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Tesi di Laurea

**Robust and probabilistic
optimization methods with
applications to truss
structures**

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*Al mio caro papà
che tutti i giorni
mi assiste e mi ama
da un Posto molto speciale.
Ciao papà!*

Sommario: metodi di ottimizzazione robusta e probabilistica con applicazioni a travi reticolari

Il lavoro svolto in questa tesi riguarda una delle innumerevoli branche applicative dell'ottimizzazione convessa: il progetto di travi reticolari. Esse consistono in un insieme di travi che si uniscono ai loro estremi - i nodi - disposti secondo un desiderato grigliato o reticolo. Codeste strutture sono estremamente diffuse in ambito industriale e civile; appaiono infatti in ponti (in particolare quelli ferroviari; i cosiddetti ponti militari), tralicci, particolari edifici, gru, eccetera. L'esempio per eccellenza di travatura reticolare è senza dubbio la celebre Tour Eiffel che è composta da più di centocinquanta travi connesse a trentamila nodi. Queste cifre palesano subito l'onerosa difficoltà - se non addirittura l'impossibilità - alla quale si perverrebbe se si tentasse di progettare una struttura in trave non banale a mano.

La filosofia alla base di questa tesi è quella di affrontare un progetto di travi reticolari di tipo robusto o probabilistico nei confronti dell'incertezza associata ai dati del problema fornendo al calcolatore la geometria reticolare (ossia la disposizione dei nodi ai quali si connettono le travi), i nodi fissi che sono quelli che sostengono la struttura e, infine, le forze esterne agenti su di essa.

Il primo capitolo è dedicato a notizie storiche sull'evoluzione delle travi reticolari, da sempre sfruttate dall'uomo, sin dai tempi della preistoria.

Al secondo capitolo vengono illustrati i concetti fisici (in particolare della meccanica) utili al progetto di una qualsiasi travatura reticolare. Questa, infatti, deve essere in equilibrio nonostante l'applicazione di carichi esterni. Ciò pertanto significa scrivere una coppia di equazioni (una per le componenti orizzontali ed una per le componenti verticali) per ogni nodo della

struttura interessanti, tra l'altro, le forze interne agenti lungo le travi. Tutte le equazioni ottenute vengono raccolte in un'unica equazione matriciale $Af + F = 0$ che, appunto, esprime, l'equilibrio della travatura. Tuttavia il sistema di equazioni trovato, peraltro lineare, non risulta essere determinato, neppure se venisse accompagnato da nuove equazioni di equilibrio inerenti l'annullarsi del momento delle forze. In altre parole, salvo in casi molto particolari in cui la struttura è ridotta al minimo (ossia non è ridondante in quanto a connessione delle travi) si dice che la travatura reticolare è una struttura indeterminata proprio perché le possibili soluzioni del sistema lineare di partenza sono infinite. Per rendere la natura del sistema da indeterminata a determinata è necessario introdurre delle nuove equazioni; questa volta non più riguardanti l'equilibrio bensì la caratteristica del materiale. Si suppone infatti che il materiale (o i materiali) costituenti la struttura non siano più rigidi bensì elastici ed obbediscano pertanto alla legge di Hooke. Con questa ipotesi, allora, si ottiene una nuova equazione per ogni trave della struttura (la legge di Hooke appunto) e la struttura non risulta più essere indeterminata.

I risultati forniti dagli algoritmi sono sia grafici che numerici. Viene infatti visualizzata la struttura finita insieme al volume delle singole travi e la cosiddetta *compliance*; l'energia elastica da minimizzare durante il progetto per garantire una maggiore stabilità alla costruzione. Come noto, infatti, nella legge di Hooke compare la sezione trasversale della trave. Questa è l'unica variabile gestibile in fase di ottimizzazione. Le lunghezze delle travi, infatti, sono fissate dalla geometria iniziale del problema imposta dal progettista. Agendo invece sulle sezioni (e quindi sui singoli volumi) delle travi costituenti la travatura, è allora possibile minimizzare la compliance per rendere la struttura la più stabile possibile.

Il progetto sfocia pertanto in un problema di ottimizzazione dove la compliance gioca il ruolo della funzione costo da minimizzare espressa, tra l'altro, in maniera tale da risultare convessa cosicché si possono sfruttare i notevoli vantaggi offerti dalla teoria dell'ottimizzazione convessa presentata al terzo capitolo.

Al quarto capitolo il progetto viene condotto ad una formulazione ancora più vantaggiosa; quella di tipo LMI. Tale acronimo deriva dall'inglese *Linear Matrix Inequalities*. Si tratta cioè di disuguaglianze matriciali, ma soprattutto *lineari*. La trasformazione dal problema convesso non lineare a problema convesso LMI avviene sfruttando una particolare proprietà del complemento di Schur.

Il quinto capitolo, infine, considera il problema del progetto di travature reticolare, questa volta nella condizione peggiore in cui i dati sono affetti da incertezza. Eventuali carichi o materiali costituenti la struttura, infatti, possono essere incerti. In tal caso occorre generalizzare gli algoritmi di partenza per tenere in conto la presenza dell'incertezza nei dati. Vengono analizzati algoritmi sia di tipo robusto che di tipo probabilistico. Gli algoritmi di tipo

robusto consistono nel minimizzare il caso peggiore. Si effettuano, tra l'altro, delle maggiorazioni sull'incertezza. Geometricamente parlando, ciò consiste nel descrivere l'incertezza entro un politopo o un ellissoide che lo racchiuda ulteriormente. È sufficiente conoscere i vertici del politopo o la matrice relativa all'ellissoide per ottenere una soluzione esatta del problema incerto. Viceversa l'algoritmo probabilistico fornisce una soluzione estraendo un numero finito di campioni incerti. Chiaramente tale procedimento dà luogo ad un risultato approssimato. Tuttavia è possibile fissare a priori l'accuratezza desiderata della soluzione e la cosiddetta probabilità di violazione. Da questi due valori si ricava il numero di campioni da estrarre al fine di ottenere un siffatto risultato.

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Abstract

The work reported in this thesis is about one of the many branches of convex optimization: the truss structures design. A truss is a collection of bars which meet each other at certain points - the nodes - to form a planar or spatial lattice. Truss structures are ubiquitous and widespread in the industrialized and civil world; they appear as bridges, towers, roof supports, building exoskeletons, cranes and so on everywhere. The most famous and popular example of truss structure is the Eiffel tower, which has more than 15000 girders connected at over 30000 points. These numbers give the straightforward idea that it would be almost impossible (particularly in complex cases) and tedious to design a truss structures by hand; hence design algorithms are required.

The philosophy at the basis of this thesis is to handle a robust or probabilistic truss structures design towards uncertainty associated to the data of the problem by providing to the processor the lattice geometry (i.e. position of nodes where the bars meet each other), the fixed nodes holding the structure and, finally, the external forces acting on the truss.

Chapter one is about historical news on the evolution of truss structures. Humanity, in fact, has been exploiting them since prehistory.

In chapter two physical principles useful to start a truss structures design are introduced. The structure must be balanced although the presence of external loads. Equilibrium condition translates then into writing a couple of equations (one for horizontal force components and another one for vertical force components) for every node of the structure also regarding internal forces acting along the beams. All these equations can be gathered into a unique matrix equation $Af + F = 0$ that just expresses equilibrium of the truss. Nevertheless such a system of linear equations admits an infinity of possible solution hence is overdetermined. It would still be overdetermined even if new equilibrium equations about zero force moment were added. Therefore except for very simple cases where the truss is minimum the system has an infinity of solution and the truss is said to be an indeterminate structure. New equations are then required to solve the system. Such new equations are about the elastic nature of the materials involved in the structure. With this hypothesis an equation for every rod (the Hooke's law) is then obtained and the structure is no longer indeterminate.

The yielded results are both graphical and numerical. Indeed at the end of every algorithm the final structure is visualized together with every single rod volume and the so-called *compliance*: the elastic energy to minimize during the design to assure the greatest stability of the truss. Cross sectional area is involved in Hooke's law and it is the only free variable during optimization. Rods lengths, indeed, are determined by the geometry of the lattice which is set by the designer. Acting on the sections (hence on the volumes) of the bars it is then possible to minimize the truss to make it as stable as possible.

Therefore the truss structures design is an optimization problem where the compliance plays the role of the cost function. Furthermore the compliance is expressed so that to result a convex function therefore convex optimization advantages can be exploited. This is shown in chapter three.

In chapter four the problem is led to an even more advantageous formulation: the LMI one. Such acronym stands for *Linear Matrix Inequalities*. Hence the convex nonlinear problem is converted into a convex matrix linear one by exploiting a particular property of the Schur complement.

Chapter five takes uncertainty into account in the truss structures design. Loads and materials of the structure, indeed, may be uncertain. In this case the original algorithms must be generalized. Both robust and probabilistic algorithms are introduced. Robust algorithms consist in minimizing the worst case and uncertainty is enclosed into a polytope or an ellipsoide enclosing the polytope itself. It is enough to know the vertexes of the polytope or the matrix relative to the ellipsoid to get an exact solution of the uncertain problem. Vice versa the probabilistic algorithm finds a solution by extracting a finite number of uncertain samples. This way to proceed leads, of course, to an approximate result. However one can fix a priori the desired accuracy of the solution and the so-called probability of violation. Once that these two values are fixed one can calculate the number of samples to extract to get such a solution.

Chapter 1

A brief history in truss structures

This first chapter gives to the reader a historical introduction about truss bridges¹.

A first informal definition of truss is a collection of rods which meet each other at certain nodes. The rods can be in tension or in compression. This feature of the truss gives the final configuration. For instance in the Howe bridge configuration the vertical bars are in tension whilst the diagonal bars are in compression.

The history of truss structures is very ancient. It began in prehistoric times when human beings used simple beams from wood, mammoth tusks or whale ribs covered with animal skins or mud to build up the first houses.

It has then developed in time until today where many modern buildings are truss structures.

A very important application of truss structures are truss bridges. When people reflect on “historic bridges,” they most often envision wooden truss bridges. With its picturesque design, the wooden truss bridge has a near universal appeal. For many years, travelogues and historians alike have documented them and promoted their preservation, more than any other bridge type.

For centuries, builders used timber as a construction material for trusses, possibly even for truss bridges. However, it was not until 1570 that Andrea Palladio published four books on architecture, the first written documentation concerning wooden truss bridges. Palladio, the first to promote the use of wooden trusses for bridge design, described several wooden trusses designs. However, builders in Europe erected few wooden truss bridges until the eighteenth century, and then most commonly in heavily wooded coun-

¹Information expounded in this introductory chapter has been taken from [5], [28], [32] and [29, page 79]. Thanks to Franco Maria Boschetto for providing further information about truss structures history.

tries such as Switzerland.

In the early nineteenth century, a variety of builders devised various bridge designs that they promoted.

In 1840 William Howe patented the Howe truss which used metal vertical tension rods and timber diagonal compression members. This joint use of metal and wood materials for bridge components, called a “combination truss”, was a significant transitional feature in the eventual development of an all-metal truss.

In 1844 Caleb Pratt, an architect, and his engineer son Thomas designed the Pratt truss, another truss from this period that had widespread significance. While the configuration appears to be the same as a Howe truss, the Pratt truss’s verticals functioned as compression members and diagonals functioned as tension members.

Wooden truss bridges provided a means to span large crossings efficiently. These new bridges not only facilitated transportation but also increased awareness and interest in bridge building. As a result, builders developed a variety of truss types and built numerous wooden truss bridges throughout the nineteenth century, the heyday of wooden truss design. At the same time, the construction of wooden truss bridges heightened awareness of the potential of truss designs and resulted in new variations in iron and later steel bridges. Even though builders erected a small number of wooden truss bridges into the twentieth century, beginning in the mid-nineteenth century, evolving designs in metal eventually eclipsed the use of wooden truss bridges and rendered them virtually obsolete by the end of the nineteenth century.

But why are truss structures so widespread? The importance of these structures can be found and seen even in everyday life: cranes, railroad bridges, buildings, the Eiffel tower and so on. Figures from 1.2 to 1.7 show a truss bridge located between Piedmont and Lombardia crossing the Ticino river and linking the towns of Oleggio (Novara) and Lonate Pozzolo (Varese). The main material is steel and it has been build since 1887 to 1889, in that period of time (since the second half of the nineteenth century) where iron and steel were widely used in constructions such as bridges and many architectural monuments such as the Eiffel tower (see figure 1.1), Paris, France, built in 1889 and the Statue of libery, New York, USA, built in 1886.

The most popular and imposing truss structure in the world is no doubt the Eiffel tower. It was built in 1889 by Gustave Eiffel and it was designed for the *International Exposition*. At first it was thought to be taken down at the end of the exhibition but that never happened. It’s a real masterpiece: it is 320 meters high; it weighs 7000 tons and it has more than 15000 girders connected at over 30000 points.

Figure 1.1: The Eiffel tower, Paris, France. Thanks to Bruna Caser Pidello for taking this picture.

Figure 1.2: The bridge on the Ticino river linking Oleggio to Lonate Pozzolo, Italy.

Figure 1.3: An internal view of the truss bridge.

Figure 1.4: Bridge entrance from the side of the town of Oleggio (Novara), Piedmont.

Figure 1.5: An external view of the truss bridge.

Figure 1.6: Bridge entrance from the side of the town of Lonate Pozzolo (Varese), Lombardia.

Figure 1.7: The Truss bridge and the Ticino River, Italy.

Figure 1.8: A crane.

Chapter 2

Introduction to truss structures

A truss is a mechanical structure made up of a set of bars which meet each other at certain nodes. Hence a truss is a collection of m bars and n nodes. The nodes can be static (fixed in place) or free (movable when the truss is stressed). The structure can be bidimensional ($d = 2$) or tridimensional ($d = 3$). A truss structure is designed, fabricated and assembled such that its members carry the loads in tension or compression. More abstractly, a truss structure is made up of straight, two-force members, fastened together by frictionless pins; all loads are applied at the joints.

In this chapter, theory concerning truss structures will be developed taking into account the following notation:

- m is the number of bars of the whole truss structure;
- n is the number of the nodes of the whole truss structure;
- p is the number of the free nodes of the whole truss structure; the number of fixed nodes is hence $n - p$;
- d is the dimension of the structures; in other words, $d = 2$ means the truss is bidimensional, whilst $d = 3$ means the truss is tridimensional;
- N is the number of degrees of freedom of the structure; in other words every free node has, of course, d degrees of freedom, so the total number N of degrees of freedom is given by the number of free nodes times the dimension d of the structure, i.e.

$$N = p \times d.$$

Since the truss has n nodes in all, it follows that, at most,

$$N \leq n \times d.$$

- F is a vector of external forces which manifest on the structure. Note that $F \in \mathbb{R}^N$, since forces apply to free nodes and every force has d components;
- such forces F cause internal forces which will be collected into a proper vector f . An internal force apply uniquely on a bar, hence it only has one component (along the bar itself) which counteracts (for the third Newton's law) the resultant of external forces at that bar. Since the structure has m bars and internal forces has one component only and there's one internal force for every bar, then $f \in \mathbb{R}^m$.
- these forces will cause displacements of free nodes. The vector containing the (small) displacements will be indicated as u . Since only free nodes can move, it follows that $u \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

Other useful information concerning the truss structure is:

- the length L_k of bar k , where $k = 1, \dots, m$;
- the Young's modulus E_k of bar k , where $k = 1, \dots, m$;
- the volume t_k of bar k , where $k = 1, \dots, m$.

These concepts will be developed with a more degree of accuracy later in the chapter, after an introduction, for the sake of completeness, on the mechanics which holds behind truss structure.

2.1 The concept of force and Newton's third law

In common language, a force is something which pushes or pulls. Forces are the result on interactions among two or more bodies: if body A interacts with body B, then even B interacts with A. Hence forces take action in pairs. That branch of physics which studies how forces affect motion is called *dynamic*. The fundamental dynamic principia are described by the three Newton's law. It is convenient introduce, at first, Newton's third law:

Newton's third law (simple) : *For every action there is an equal and opposite reaction, or all forces occur in pairs, and these two forces are equal in magnitude and opposite in direction.*

This formulation is the well-known simplification of the same law expressed in the strong form:

Newton's third law (strong form) : *Whenever a particle A exerts*

a force on another particle B , B simultaneously exerts a force on A with the same magnitude in the opposite direction. These two forces act along the same line.

♣

Newton's third law appears in truss structures when the internal force of a beam counteracts the effect of external forces on the beam itself. As depicted in figure (2.1), when bar k is under expansion, its internal force counteracts expansion with compression and $f_k \geq 0$. Vice versa, when bar k is under compression, its internal force counteracts compression with expansion and $f_k \leq 0$. Newton's first and second laws are now introduced. As in every other mechanic problem, they will also be useful in truss structures analysis.

A bar under expansion

A bar under compression

Figure 2.1: Third Newton's law applied to a bar of a truss.

2.2 Newton's first law: Newton's law of inertia

Newton's first law : *If no net force acts on a particle, then it is possible to select a set of reference frames, called inertial reference frames, observed from which the particle moves without any change in velocity (i.e. acceleration of the particle equals zero).*

♣

Newton's first law is a property of certain reference frames. Acceleration of a body, in general, depends on the choice of the reference frame into which

it is measured. Laws of classical mechanics are only valid in certain reference frames, more precisely for those where *the same value of acceleration* is measured. Tendency for a body not to move or to proceed with uniform motion is called *inertia*. Newton's first law is also known as law of inertia and all those reference frames where it holds are called *inertial reference frames*. Given an inertial reference frame, any other reference frame which moves with uniform motion respect to it, is inertial. Newton's first law is also expressed in the following equivalent form:

Newton's first law: equivalent formulation : *If no net force acts on a body, it will stay at rest if it is staying at rest or it continues its motion at a constant velocity if it is moving at a constant velocity.*

2.3 Newton's second law

Newton's second law : *Observed from an inertial reference frame, the net force on a particle is proportional to the time rate of change of its linear momentum, i.e.*

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt}$$

But $\mathbf{p} = m \mathbf{v}$, hence

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(m\mathbf{v}) = m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = m \mathbf{a}$$

and Newton's second law can also be expressed as:

Newton's second law (equivalent form) : *If a net force \mathbf{F} acts on a body with mass m , it will undergo an acceleration \mathbf{a} , given by the following relation:*

$$\mathbf{F} = m \mathbf{a}.$$

Note that \mathbf{F} is a *net force*, which is given by summing up all partial forces applying on the particle of mass m , i.e.

$$\mathbf{F} = \sum_i \mathbf{F}_i = m \mathbf{a} \tag{2.1}$$

Note also as Newton's second law contains Newton's first law as a particular case; if, indeed, the net force applying on the body is zero, one has the following:

$$\mathbf{F} = m \mathbf{a} \implies 0 = m \mathbf{a} \implies \mathbf{a} = 0.$$

But $\mathbf{a} = 0$ means that the body is staying at rest or it is moving at constant velocity, hence Newton's first law is obtained. For further details see, for instance, [19] and [9].

2.4 Equilibrium problems

Now that Newton's laws have been introduced, two main classes of problems can be discussed. The first class of problems is about those situations where the resultant force is nonzero and an acceleration exists. Such variety of scenarios is known as *non equilibrium problems*. In the second class of problems, vice versa, the net force is zero and hence the system doesn't move or it moves uniformly in velocity. This condition is known as *equilibrium* and the regarding problems are called *equilibrium problems*. Attention will be devoted on equilibrium problems since the truss designer wants its structure to be stable, i.e. it doesn't fall down but it neither moves. In facing out equilibrium problems one should keep in mind that there's no acceleration and so, due to Newton's second law,

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \mathbf{F}_i = \mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 + \dots + \mathbf{F}_M = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

where M is the total number of forces acting on the considered body. This vectorial equation decomposes into two scalar equations (one for the x direction and another one for the y direction) if $d = 2$ or into three scalar equation (one for the x direction, one for the y direction and, finally, one for the z direction) if $d = 3$. Note that one can choose different axis (i.e. not x , y nor z) on which to decompose equation (2.2) if these are more convenient than the cartesian ones.

In the following lines an example of equilibrium problem is given. Newton's laws must be used to solve the problem, which is illustrated in picture (2.2). In this problem the unknowns are forces on cables AB and BC , given the angles θ_A and θ_B and mass M of the block held by the cables. This example is very useful because the technique which is going to be shown will be used in delving with truss problems.

Figure (2.3) shows the same problem with the chosen reference axis (which, in this case, are the cartesian ones), angles and forces decomposition. Since this is an equilibrium problem $\mathbf{a} = 0$ and, by Newton's second

Figure 2.2: A simple structure.

law $\sum_i \mathbf{F} = 0$. In this examples the involved forces are \mathbf{F}_A (on cable AB), \mathbf{F}_C (on cable BC) and \mathbf{W} (gravity force), with $\mathbf{W} = M \mathbf{g}$ hence

$$\mathbf{F}_A + \mathbf{F}_C + \mathbf{W} = 0.$$

This vectorial equation decomposes into two scalar equations, one for every reference axis (in this case x and y):

$$\begin{cases} F_{Ax} + F_{Cx} + W_x = 0 \\ F_{Ay} + F_{Cy} + W_y = 0 \end{cases}$$

But gravity force is perpendicularly oriented, i.e. it has no orizontal component, i.e. $W_x = 0$, hence equations above simplify to

$$\begin{cases} F_{Ax} + F_{Cx} = 0 \\ F_{Ay} + F_{Cy} + W_y = 0. \end{cases}$$

Now, looking at figure (2.3) the latter equations can be further expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} -F_A \cos \theta_A + F_C \cos \theta_B = 0 \\ F_A \sin \theta_A + F_C \sin \theta_B - Mg = 0 \end{cases}$$

where **force components according to the positive orientation of the axis has been considered *positive***, whilst force components

Figure 2.3: A simple structure with its reference axis, angle notation and forces decomposition.

opposite to the positive orientation of the axis has been considered *negative*. With this convention, in fact, one finds out

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{Ax} &= -F_A \cos \theta_A \\
 F_{Ay} &= F_A \sin \theta_A \\
 F_{Cx} &= F_C \cos \theta_B \\
 F_{Cy} &= F_C \sin \theta_B \\
 W_y &= -M g.
 \end{aligned}$$

Here follow the remaining steps required to find F_A and F_C and, hence, to solve the problem:

$$\begin{cases} F_A \cos \theta_A - F_C \cos \theta_B = 0 \\ F_A \sin \theta_A + F_C \sin \theta_B = M g \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_A & -\cos \theta_B \\ \sin \theta_A & \sin \theta_B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_A \\ F_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ M g \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta &= \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta_A & -\cos \theta_B \\ \sin \theta_A & \sin \theta_B \end{vmatrix} = \\
 &= \cos \theta_A \sin \theta_B + \sin \theta_A \cos \theta_B = \\
 &= \sin \theta_A \cos \theta_B + \cos \theta_A \sin \theta_B = \\
 &= \sin(\theta_A + \theta_B).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta_A = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\cos \theta_B \\ Mg & \sin \theta_B \end{vmatrix} = \cos \theta_B Mg = Mg \cos \theta_B.$$

$$\Delta_C = \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta_A & 0 \\ \sin \theta_A & Mg \end{vmatrix} = \cos \theta_A Mg = Mg \cos \theta_A.$$

Now, forces F_A and F_C are found as the ratios of the previously calculated determinants:

$$F_A = \frac{\Delta_A}{\Delta} = \frac{Mg \cos \theta_B}{\sin(\theta_A + \theta_B)} = Mg \frac{\cos \theta_B}{\sin(\theta_A + \theta_B)} \quad (2.3)$$

$$F_C = \frac{\Delta_C}{\Delta} = \frac{Mg \cos \theta_A}{\sin(\theta_A + \theta_B)} = Mg \frac{\cos \theta_A}{\sin(\theta_A + \theta_B)} \quad (2.4)$$

The example is over, but some interesting observations can be made by looking at equations (2.4) and (2.4), which are:

- the relations between tensions F_A and F_C and the weight W are *linear*, hence if, for instance, weight W doubles, so do tensions F_A and F_C ;
- the more vertically oriented of the two cables (i.e. the one leading an angle θ closer to a right angle), experiences the greater of the two tensions, in other words *it carries the greatest load*;
- the tension in the cables can be greater than the weight of the suspended body. In fact as θ_A and θ_B approach zero, $\sin(\theta_A + \theta_B)$ and hence the denominator approaches zero, whilst $\cos \theta_A$ and $\cos \theta_B$ (hence the numerator) approach one, with the consequence that F_A and F_C become greater than weight W ;
- when the system is symmetric, i.e. $\theta_A = \theta_B \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \theta$, the tensions on the two cables are equal, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} F_A = F_C &= Mg \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin(\theta + \theta)} = \\ &= Mg \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin 2\theta} = \\ &= Mg \frac{\cos \theta}{2 \sin \theta \cos \theta} = \\ &= \frac{Mg}{2 \sin \theta} \\ &\quad \forall \theta \mid \cos \theta \neq 0 \implies \\ &\implies \forall \theta \neq \frac{\pi}{2} + 2k\pi, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}; \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

- if both angles approach a right angle, i.e. $\theta_A = \theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\theta_B = \theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}$, by using (2.5) one gets:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_A = F_C &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}} Mg \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin 2\theta} = \\
 &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{Mg \cos \theta}{2 \sin \theta \cos \theta} = \\
 &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{Mg}{2 \sin \theta} = \\
 &= \frac{Mg}{2 \sin \frac{\pi}{2}} = \\
 &= \frac{Mg}{2} = \\
 &= \frac{W}{2},
 \end{aligned}$$

so each cable picks up half the weight.

2.5 Equilibrium problems applied to trusses

The theory exposed in previous sections and the technique shown in the last example is fundamental in the design of a truss structure. *The most important property of a truss, indeed, is that it must be stable, i.e. it mustn't fall down and neither move.* Hence, for a truss structure to be stable, none of its joints must be out of force balance. The first step to do is, hence, to apply equilibrium conditions (using the same technique of the latter example) *for each free node*. This procedure will be now led referring to the truss depicted in figure (2.4).

The convention is to number the nodes progressively from the left to the right and from the bottom to the top. To simplify the notation bars will be labeled with the number (in a crescent order) of the two nodes they link to, e.g. L_{14} indicates the beam connecting node 1 with node 4. We assume the shortest beam length to be L , so we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{12} &= L \\
 L_{13} &= L \\
 L_{14} &= \sqrt{2}L \\
 L_{16} &= \sqrt{5}L \\
 L_{23} &= \sqrt{2}L \\
 L_{24} &= L \\
 L_{25} &= \sqrt{5}L \\
 L_{34} &= L
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.4: A truss problem.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{35} &= L \\
 L_{36} &= \sqrt{2}L \\
 L_{45} &= \sqrt{2}L \\
 L_{46} &= L \\
 L_{56} &= L.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note, also, that there are two degrees of freedom ($d = 2$, hence the truss is *planar*), there are thirteen bars ($m = 13$) and there are six nodes ($n = 6$) of whom two are fixed -nodes one and five- and four are free, i.e. $p = 4$. Let's start at node two; looking at figure (2.5) we write two equilibrium equations, one for the x component and another one for the y component.

Note that, to determine, for instance, the x and y components of f_{25} on the coordinate axis, one need to know, respectively, the cosine and the sine of the acute angle between f_{25} itself and the x axis. Let θ_{25} be the acute angle between f_{25} and the x axis, then, looking at figure (2.6) we get

$$\sin \theta_{25} = \frac{L_{56}}{L_{25}} = \frac{L}{\sqrt{5}L} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}},$$

and

$$\cos \theta_{25} = \frac{L_{24} + L_{46}}{L_{25}} = \frac{L + L}{\sqrt{5}L} = \frac{2L}{\sqrt{5}L} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}.$$

Similarly, looking at figure (2.7), we can calculate both $\sin \theta_{23}$ and $\cos \theta_{23}$ as follows:

Figure 2.5: Equilibrium conditions at node two.

Figure 2.6: How to evaluate $\sin \theta_{25}$ and $\cos \theta_{25}$.

$$\sin \theta_{23} = \frac{L_{34}}{L_{23}} = \frac{L}{\sqrt{2}L} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2},$$

and

$$\cos \theta_{23} = \frac{L_{24}}{L_{23}} = \frac{L}{\sqrt{2}L} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}.$$

Figure 2.7: How to evaluate $\sin \theta_{23}$ and $\cos \theta_{23}$.

Now we are ready to write the two equilibrium equations for node two. Looking again at figure (2.5) and remembering the important convention that components according to the positive verse of the axis are considered to be positive, vice versa are negative, we get

$$f_{23} \cos \theta_{23} + f_{25} \cos \theta_{25} + f_{24} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (2.6)$$

$$-f_{12} - f_{23} \sin \theta_{23} - f_{25} \sin \theta_{25} = 0.$$

It is obvious that we will get eight equations in all: in fact there are two equations for every free node. In general, the more the number of nodes increases the more the number of equations does too. For better practice

it is convenient to express all these equations in a matrix way. To do so, it is important to introduce another convention: we express internal forces f_{ij} into equilibrium equations in crescent order, i.e., e.g. f_{23} comes first than f_{25} but after f_{12} . Respecting this new convention (which usefulness will be clear when all equations will be gathered into a matrix form), equations (2.6) become:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{23} \cos \theta_{23} + f_{24} + f_{25} \cos \theta_{25} &= 0 & \text{and} \\ -f_{12} - f_{23} \sin \theta_{23} - f_{25} \sin \theta_{25} &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

Substituting into (2.7) the various values of the sine and cosine of the involved angles, we obtain:

$$\text{NODE TWO} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{23} + f_{24} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} f_{25} = 0 \\ -f_{12} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{23} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} f_{25} = 0. \end{cases} \tag{2.8}$$

Figure (2.8) shows all the angles needed to calculate equilibrium equations and its sine and cosine values are reported in table (2.1).

Figure 2.8: Useful angles to calculate equilibrium conditions.

Now that we know the sine and the cosine of the involved angles, we are ready to determine the equilibrium equations for the remaining free nodes.

θ	$\sin \theta$	$\cos \theta$
θ_{23}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$
θ_{25}	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$	$\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$
θ_{32}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$
θ_{36}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$
θ_{41}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$
θ_{45}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$
θ_{61}	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$	$\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$
θ_{63}	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$

Table 2.1: Sine and cosine values for the angles depicted in figure (2.8).

Force F_3 acts on node three. For those nodes where external forces act we express equilibrium equations as

$$\text{internal forces} + \text{external forces} = 0$$

Hence, for node three, we have:

$$\text{III} \begin{cases} x \text{ component:} & -f_{13} - f_{23} \cos \theta_{32} + f_{36} \cos \theta_{36} + f_{35} + F_{3x} = 0 \\ y \text{ component:} & f_{23} \sin \theta_{32} + f_{34} + f_{36} \sin \theta_{36} - F_{3y} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} -f_{13} - f_{23} \cos \theta_{32} + f_{35} + f_{36} \cos \theta_{36} + F_{3x} = 0 \\ f_{23} \sin \theta_{32} + f_{34} + f_{36} \sin \theta_{36} - F_{3y} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{NODE THREE} \begin{cases} -f_{13} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{23} + f_{35} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{36} + F_{3x} = 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{23} + f_{34} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} f_{36} - F_{3y} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

At node four we have:

$$\text{IV} \begin{cases} x \text{ component:} & -f_{24} - f_{14} \cos \theta_{41} + f_{46} + f_{45} \cos \theta_{45} = 0 \\ y \text{ component:} & -f_{14} \sin \theta_{41} - f_{34} - f_{45} \sin \theta_{45} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} -f_{14} \cos \theta_{41} - f_{24} + f_{45} \cos \theta_{45} + f_{46} = 0 \\ -f_{14} \sin \theta_{41} - f_{34} - f_{45} \sin \theta_{45} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{NODE FOUR} \quad \begin{cases} -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{14} - f_{24} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{45} + f_{46} = 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{14} - f_{34} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{45} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

At node six we have:

$$\text{VI} \quad \begin{cases} x \text{ component:} & -f_{46} - f_{16} \cos \theta_{61} - f_{36} \cos \theta_{63} = 0 \\ y \text{ component:} & -f_{16} \sin \theta_{61} - f_{36} \sin \theta_{63} - f_{56} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} -f_{16} \cos \theta_{61} - f_{36} \cos \theta_{63} - f_{46} = 0 \\ -f_{16} \sin \theta_{61} - f_{36} \sin \theta_{63} - f_{56} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{NODE SIX} \quad \begin{cases} -\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}f_{16} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} - f_{46} = 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}f_{16} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} - f_{56} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

The final step regarding equilibrium conditions is to express equations (2.8), (2.9), (2.10) and (2.11) in a matrix formulation. To do so, let's start to repeat them in the selected order:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [2.8.x] \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{23} + f_{24} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}f_{25} = 0 \\ [2.8.y] \quad -f_{12} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{23} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}f_{25} = 0 \\ [2.9.x] \quad -f_{13} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{23} + f_{35} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} + F_{3x} = 0 \\ [2.9.y] \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{23} + f_{34} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} - F_{3y} = 0 \\ [2.10.x] \quad -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{14} - f_{24} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{45} + f_{46} = 0 \\ [2.10.y] \quad -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{14} - f_{34} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{45} = 0 \\ [2.11.x] \quad -\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}f_{16} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} - f_{46} = 0 \\ [2.11.y] \quad -\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}f_{16} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}f_{36} - f_{56} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (2.12)$$

Now, introducing a vector f containing all the internal forces in progressive order, and a vector F for the external forces, equation (2.12) can finally be expressed in the following matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix}
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 1 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
-1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 1 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & -1 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 & -1
\end{bmatrix}
\begin{bmatrix}
f_{12} \\
f_{13} \\
f_{14} \\
f_{16} \\
f_{23} \\
f_{24} \\
f_{25} \\
f_{34} \\
f_{35} \\
f_{36} \\
f_{45} \\
f_{46} \\
f_{56}
\end{bmatrix}
+
\begin{bmatrix}
0 \\
0 \\
F_{3x} \\
-F_{3y} \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0
\end{bmatrix}
=
\begin{bmatrix}
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0
\end{bmatrix}.
\quad (2.13)$$

Equation (2.13) can be written in the following compact matrix notation:

$$\mathbf{A}f + \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.14)$$

Without ambiguity and without loss of generality we can omit, for the sake of simplicity, the bold style in equation (2.14), keeping in mind that A is a matrix and f and F are vectors. Introducing such simplification, equation (2.14) becomes

$$\mathbf{Equilibrium\ conditions} \quad (2.15)$$

$$Af + F = 0.$$

To understand the dimensions of matrix A (and so of equation (2.15)), take a look at table (2.5) which reports matrix A with the details of node equations and internal forces components.

The number of rows of A is the number of equilibrium conditions. There are d equilibrium equations for every free nodes, so there are $p \times d$ equilibrium equations. But $p \times d$ is the number of degrees of freedom of the truss, which is indicated with N . Hence the number of rows of A is N . In this example, $p = 4$ and $d = 2$, $N = p \times d = 4 \times 2 = 8$, which is the actual number of rows of A . Note, also, that every column of A represent an internal force.

MATRIX A													
	INTERNAL FORCES												
NODES	f ₁₂	f ₁₃	f ₁₄	f ₁₆	f ₂₃	f ₂₄	f ₂₅	f ₃₄	f ₃₅	f ₃₆	f ₄₅	f ₄₆	f ₅₆
2.x	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	1	$\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.y	-1	0	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$	0	0	0	0	0	0
3.x	0	-1	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	0	1	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	0
3.y	0	0	0	0	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	1	0	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	0
4.x	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	1	0
4.y	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0
6.x	0	0	0	$-\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$	0	0	0	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	-1	0
6.y	0	0	0	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$	0	0	0	0	0	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0	0	-1

Table 2.2: Matrix A with details about its elements.

The total number of internal forces (i.e. the number of columns of A) is the number of bars of the truss, which is m .

Hence A is a $N \times m$ matrix.

In the following column k of matrix A will be denoted as a_k . Of course $1 \leq k \leq m$. Each column a_k is the projection of its associated beam onto the degrees of freedom of the nodes that bar k meets. In other words, d force balance equations are required at every free node, one for every component or degree of freedom. Every bar ends at two nodes and takes part, at such nodes, into the local balance equations. The components of bar k at the various nodes and components -which number are the degrees of freedom d - are column a_k . Consider, for instance, the bar linking node two with node three; in the progressive order introduced it is bar number five. There are, in fact, four bars before it, which are L_{12} , L_{13} , L_{14} and L_{16} . After these four bars there is L_{23} which is bar number five which internal force is f_{23} . The components of bar number five at node two (i.e. the projections of bar number five on the coordinate axis) normalized to its length L_{23} are $+\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ for the x axis and $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ for the y axis. At node three the components are

$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ for the x axis and $+\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ for the y axis. That's why

$$a_5 = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 2.x \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 2.y \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 3.x \\ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 3.y \\ 0 & 4.x \\ 0 & 4.y \\ 0 & 6.x \\ 0 & 6.y \end{array} \right].$$

System (2.13) is a $N \times m$ set of equations. The number of bars, as in this case, is, in general, greater than the total number of degrees of freedom. In this example we have to solve a 8×13 system which leads to an indeterminate system with an infinity of solutions. Therefore force balance equations are not enough in the study of truss structures. Other concepts, such as momentum, friction force and elasticity must be introduced to solve the problem. This will be done in the following, starting with friction force, introduced in the next section. The concept of momentum must be introduced when dealing with bodies that cannot be represented as points (such as trusses). Although momentum is very important in truss design it will not be still enough (as a balance force equation) in the contribution to the solution of (2.13). That's why the truss is called an *undeterminate structure*. Only by introducing elasticity one can reach a sufficient number of equations and then determine the displacements u .

2.6 Friction force

Consider an object lying on a surface, as depicted in figure (2.9.a). Friction is that kind of force which takes place tending to resist motion. It acts parallel to the plane of contact of the object and the ground. Friction force is expressed as F_f and is related to the normal force N of the object through the *coefficient of friction* μ :

$$F_f = \mu N.$$

There are actually two types of coefficients of friction: the coefficient of static friction and the coefficient of dynamic friction. The coefficient of static friction is used when an external applied force F to the object (see figure (2.9.b)) is not strong enough to contrast friction force F_f and hence the object doesn't move. This is the case of static equilibrium. Particularly the coefficient of static friction is defined at the condition of *impending motion*, which means that a force just a little bit above μN is enough to

move the object. Therefore friction force always acts in a direction resisting the motion. It depends upon the the surface materials which are in contact at the interface between the object and the plane but *not* upon the area in contact. Friction force takes into account that surfaces of the plane and of the object posing or sliding on it are never perfectly plain but there are always roughnesses (coarsenesses) on them. Such imperfections counteracts motion of the body. If the body is moving the effect of interaction between roughnesses (therefore friction force) decreases; that's why the coefficient of dynamic friction is lower that the coefficient of static friction. Figure (2.9) shows an example of how friction force tends to resist motion. In figures (2.9.a) and (2.9.b) the applied force F pulls the object, so friction force acts from the right to the left. Contrariwise in figures (2.9.a), (2.9.b) and (2.9.c) the applied force F pushes the object and friction force acts from the left to the right. We assume to be at impending motion, hence the coefficient of friction is maximum and the object still doesn't move and static equilibrium holds.

Figure 2.9: An example on friction force application.

If the applied force F pulls the object, the equilibrium equations are:

$$\begin{cases} \text{x axis} & F \cos \theta - F_f = 0 \\ \text{y axis} & F \sin \theta + N - W = 0 \end{cases}$$

But $F_f = \mu N$ therefore we get

$$\begin{cases} F \cos \theta - \mu N = 0 \\ F \sin \theta + N = W \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\mu \\ \sin \theta & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F \\ N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ W \end{bmatrix}.$$

Solving this linear system with respect to F and N via Cramer's rule we get

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta & -\mu \\ \sin \theta & 1 \end{vmatrix} = \cos \theta + \mu \sin \theta$$

$$\Delta_F = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\mu \\ W & 1 \end{vmatrix} = \mu W$$

$$\Delta_N = \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & W \end{vmatrix} = W \cos \theta.$$

$$F = \frac{\Delta_F}{\Delta} = \frac{\mu}{\cos \theta + \mu \sin \theta} W$$

$$N = \frac{\Delta_N}{\Delta} = \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos \theta + \mu \sin \theta} W$$

For the second part of the example we have:

$$\begin{cases} \text{x component} & -F \cos \theta + F_f = 0 \\ \text{y component} & -F \sin \theta - W + N = 0 \end{cases}$$

Again, $F_f = \mu N$, therefore we have:

$$\begin{cases} -F \cos \theta + \mu N = 0 \\ -F \sin \theta - W + N = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} F \cos \theta - \mu N = 0 \\ F \sin \theta - N = -W \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\mu \\ \sin \theta & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F \\ N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -W \end{bmatrix} \\ \Delta &= \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta & -\mu \\ \sin \theta & -1 \end{vmatrix} = -\cos \theta + \mu \sin \theta \\ \Delta_F &= \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\mu \\ -W & -1 \end{vmatrix} = -W\mu \\ \Delta &= \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & -W \end{vmatrix} = -W \cos \theta \\ F &= \frac{\Delta_F}{\Delta} = \frac{\mu}{\cos \theta - \mu \sin \theta} W \\ N &= \frac{\Delta_N}{\Delta} = \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos \theta - \mu \sin \theta} W \end{aligned}$$

2.7 The concept of moment

When the bodies are non puntiform, force balance equations coming from Newton's laws under static conditions are not enough. Extended bodies (which is the case of the truss) mustn't rotate or swing at equilibrium. This condition is met by imposing the moment be equal to zero. In fact, when bodies can't no longer be considered as particles they are said to be *extended bodies* and the concept of (force) moment or torque can be interpreted as the turning effect of a force. Therefore the torque or moment about an axis, due to a force F , is the effectiveness of the force in producing rotation about that axis. It is defined in the following way:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{F};$$

then

$$\tau = r F \sin \theta;$$

where r is the radial distance from the axis to the point of application of the force \mathbf{F} and θ is the acute angle between the lines of action of \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{r} , as shown in figure 2.10.

Often this definition is written in terms of the *lever arm* of the force which is the perpendicular distance from the axis to the line of the force. Note that the lever arm is $r \sin \theta$ and the torque becomes

Figure 2.10: An extended body (in light blue) and force moment definition.

$$\tau = (\text{lever arm}) (F).$$

2.8 Conditions for equilibrium

The two conditions for equilibrium of a rigid object under the action of coplanar forces are

1. the first condition for equilibrium is the force condition

$$\sum_i F_{x,i} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i F_{y,i} = 0.$$

2. the second condition for equilibrium is the torque condition; taking an axis perpendicular to the plane of the coplanar forces and calling the torques that tend to cause clockwise rotation about the axis negative, and counterclockwise torques positive; then the sum of all the torques acting on the rigid body must be zero:

$$\sum_i \tau_i = 0.$$

2.9 Elasticity: stress and strain

So far the truss has been conceived as rigid, which means it has not been considered as an elastic body. A material is said to be elastic if it deforms under *stress* - for instance an external applied force or the tension on a beam - but then returns to its original shape when the stress is removed. The amount of deformation is called *strain*.

The elastic regime is characterized by a linear relationship between stress and strain, called Hooke's law.

Stress, defined as force per unit area, is a measure of the intensity of the total internal forces acting within a body across imaginary internal surfaces, as a reaction to external applied forces.

Strain is the expression of deformation caused by the action of stress on an elastic body.

Stress and strain take place, in general, in all the d directions. In this thesis only one dimensional stress and strain will be considered. With this assumption, one-dimensional stress is defined as

$$\sigma = \frac{\text{applied force}}{\text{section}} = \frac{F}{A}. \quad (2.16)$$

One-dimensional strain is defined as the relative change in length (for instance of the beam of a bar):

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} = \frac{l - l_0}{l_0}. \quad (2.17)$$

The change in length Δl is termed the stretch, absolute strain or extension; l_0 is the original length of the material, l is the current length and ε is the (relative) strain. The extension Δl is positive if the material has gained length (tensile or normal stress or tension) and negative if it has reduced length (compressive stress).

2.10 Elasticity: Hooke's law

Figure (2.11.a) shows a spring at rest. On the left part of the spring it has been labeled a convenient point P which, when no external force is applied on the spring, is at position $x = P$. If now an external force is applied on the spring, as in figure (2.11.b), a restoring internal force \mathbf{F} appears to counteract the external force. The spring changes its length and points P changes position at $x = P'$. The total displacement of the spring is

$$\mathbf{x} = (P' - P) \hat{x}.$$

Nota that, if the force had been applied on the opposite verse, the length of the spring would have increased than lowering, i.e. point P' would have

found itself on the left of point P . This phenomenon is expressed into Hooke's law:

$$\mathbf{F} = -k\mathbf{x} \quad (2.18)$$

In equation (2.18) k is the spring constant (Newtons per meter), \mathbf{x} is the distance that the spring has been stretched or compressed away from the equilibrium position, which is the position where the spring would naturally come to rest. \mathbf{F} is the applied (restoring) force. There is a negative sign on the right hand side of the equation because the restoring force always acts in the opposite direction of the \mathbf{x} displacement (when the spring is compressed to the right, it pushes back to the left).

Figure 2.11: A spring at rest and subject to an external force \mathbf{F} .

Consider a rod of an elastic material of length L and cross-sectional area A ; it can be seen as a linear spring where the relative extension (strain) ε is linearly proportional to its tensile stress σ by a constant factor, the modulus of elasticity, often known as Young's modulus, E :

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon. \quad (2.19)$$

But $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$ and $\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L}$ so Hooke's law becomes

$$\frac{F}{A} = E \frac{\Delta L}{L}. \quad (2.20)$$

Depending on the stress intensity elastic materials may not obey to Hooke's law, i.e., the material is out of the linear region where Hooke's law takes place. Figure (2.12) shows a qualitative stress-strain curve for elastic materials. We assume small displacements for the bars of the truss and stresses such that the materials which make up the whole structure are always in the linear region so that Hooke's law holds.

Figure 2.12: Qualitative stress-strain curve for elastic materials.

2.11 Displacements of nodes within the truss

Now that we are conceiving the truss made up of elastic materials obeying to Hooke's law, internal forces f_i will cause lengths of bars to change. Therefore free nodes will undergo small displacements which are collected into a column vector u . Since only free nodes can move, u is a vector which

size is N . Figure (2.13) shows the original truss with node two undergoing a small displacement of components $(-\lambda, -\lambda)$ from its original position.

Figure 2.13: Displacement analysis at node two.

Hence

$$u = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda \\ -\lambda \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now that node two has changed its position, some bars will change its length. The following analysis calculates these new length and the variation in length. Remember that the order of the bars is

$$L_{12}, L_{13}, L_{14}, L_{16}, L_{23}, L_{24}, L_{25}, L_{34}, L_{35}, L_{36}, L_{45}, L_{46} \text{ and } L_{56}.$$

L_{12} changes its length. The old length is L . Its new length \hat{L}_{12} is found by concentrating on triangle $AO'B$; we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
O'B^2 + O'A^2 &= AB^2 \\
AB^2 &= O'B^2 + O'A^2 \\
\hat{L}_{12}^2 &= \lambda^2 + (L - \lambda)^2 \\
\hat{L}_{12}^2 &= \lambda^2 + L^2 - 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 \\
\hat{L}_{12}^2 &= 2\lambda^2 - 2L\lambda + L^2 \\
\hat{L}_{12}^2 &= 2\lambda(\lambda - L) + L^2 \\
\hat{L}_{12}^2 &= L^2 + 2\lambda(\lambda - L) \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= \sqrt{L^2 + 2\lambda(\lambda - L)} \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= \sqrt{L^2 \left(1 + \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}\right)} \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= \sqrt{L^2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}} \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= L \sqrt{1 + \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}} \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}}. \tag{2.21}
\end{aligned}$$

Note that, for $x \rightarrow 0$ then

$$\sqrt[n]{1+x} \sim 1 + \frac{x}{n}. \tag{2.22}$$

This approximation is a linearization for the n-th root coming from Taylor's formula; for further details see [36]. Particularly, the general first order approximation is, for $x \rightarrow 0$

$$(1+x)^m \sim 1 + mx. \tag{2.23}$$

Since $\sqrt{\alpha} = \alpha^{\frac{1}{2}}$, then $m = \frac{1}{2}$ and, for our case, (2.23) becomes

$$\sqrt{1+x} \sim 1 + \frac{1}{2}x \tag{2.24}$$

Using this approximation into (2.21) we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}} \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{2\lambda(\lambda - L)}{L^2}\right) \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \left(1 + \lambda \frac{\lambda - L}{L^2}\right) \tag{2.25}
\end{aligned}$$

Equation (2.25) is the approximated new length of bar one. The change in length $\Delta_1 = \hat{L}_{12} - L_{12}$ is found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \left(1 + \lambda \frac{\lambda-L}{L^2}\right) \\
\hat{L}_{12} &= L_{12} \lambda \frac{\lambda-L}{L^2} L_{12} \\
\Delta_1 &= \hat{L}_{12} - L_{12} = \lambda \frac{\lambda-L}{L^2} L_{12} \\
\Delta_1 &= \lambda \frac{\lambda-L}{L^2} L \\
\Delta_1 &= \lambda \frac{\lambda-L}{L} \\
\Delta_1 &= \lambda \left(\frac{\lambda}{L} - \frac{L}{L}\right) \\
\Delta_1 &= \lambda \left(\frac{\lambda}{L} - 1\right)
\end{aligned}$$

But, since the displacement is very small, then $\lambda \ll L$ hence $\frac{\lambda}{L} \simeq 0$ and the approximation becomes linear:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_1 &= \lambda(-1) \\
\Delta_1 &= -\lambda
\end{aligned}$$

For the other bars we have:

$$\hat{L}_{13} = L_{13} = L \quad \Delta_2 = \hat{L}_{13} - L_{13} = L - L = 0 \quad (2.26)$$

$$\hat{L}_{14} = L_{14} = \sqrt{2}L \quad \Delta_3 = \hat{L}_{14} - L_{14} = \sqrt{2}L - \sqrt{2}L = 0 \quad (2.27)$$

$$\hat{L}_{16} = L_{16} = \sqrt{5}L \quad \Delta_4 = \hat{L}_{16} - L_{16} = \sqrt{5}L - \sqrt{5}L = 0 \quad (2.28)$$

About L_{23} we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
O'C^2 + O'A^2 &= AC^2 \\
(L + \lambda)^2 + (L - \lambda)^2 &= \hat{L}_{23}^2 \\
\hat{L}_{23}^2 &= L^2 + 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 + L^2 - 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 \\
\hat{L}_{23}^2 &= 2L^2 + 2\lambda^2 \\
\hat{L}_{23}^2 &= 2(L^2 + \lambda^2) \\
\hat{L}_{23} &= \sqrt{2(L^2 + \lambda^2)} \\
\hat{L}_{23} &= \sqrt{2L^2 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}\right)} \\
\hat{L}_{23} &= \sqrt{2}L \sqrt{1 + \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}}
\end{aligned}$$

But $L_{23} = \sqrt{2}L$, therefore we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{L}_{23} &= L_{23} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \\
\hat{L}_{23} &\sim L_{23} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}\right) \\
\hat{L}_{23} &\sim L_{23} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{L_{23}}{L} \frac{\lambda^2}{L} \\
\Delta_5 &= \hat{L}_{23} - L_{23} \sim \frac{1}{2} \frac{L_{23}}{L} \frac{\lambda^2}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\lambda \ll L$ and λ is supposed to be small, then $\frac{\lambda^2}{L} \sim 0$ and

$$\Delta_5 = \hat{L}_{23} - L_{23} \sim L - L = 0 \quad (2.29)$$

About L_{24} we have:

$$\begin{aligned} OD^2 + OA^2 &= AD^2 \\ (L + \lambda)^2 + \lambda^2 &= \hat{L}_{24}^2 \\ \hat{L}_{24}^2 &= L^2 + 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 + \lambda^2 \\ \hat{L}_{24}^2 &= L^2 + 2L\lambda + 2\lambda^2 \\ \hat{L}_{24} &= \sqrt{L^2 + 2L\lambda + 2\lambda^2} \\ \hat{L}_{24} &= \sqrt{L^2 \left(1 + \frac{2L\lambda}{L^2} + \frac{2\lambda^2}{L^2}\right)} \\ \hat{L}_{24} &= \sqrt{L^2} \sqrt{1 + 2\frac{\lambda}{L} + 2\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \\ \hat{L}_{24} &= L\sqrt{1 + 2\frac{\lambda}{L} + 2\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \end{aligned}$$

But $L_{24} = L$, therefore we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{L}_{24} &= L_{24} \sqrt{1 + 2\frac{\lambda}{L} + 2\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \\ \hat{L}_{24} &\sim L_{24} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(2\frac{\lambda}{L} + 2\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}\right)\right] \\ \hat{L}_{24} &\sim L_{24} + L_{24} \left(\frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}\right) \\ \hat{L}_{24} - L_{24} &\sim \frac{L_{24}}{L} \lambda + \frac{L_{24}}{L} \frac{\lambda^2}{L} \\ \Delta_5 = \hat{L}_{24} - L_{24} &\sim \frac{L}{L} \lambda + \frac{L}{L} \frac{\lambda^2}{L} \\ \Delta_5 &\sim \lambda + \frac{\lambda^2}{L} \end{aligned}$$

Again, since $\lambda \ll L$ and λ is supposed to be small, then $\frac{\lambda^2}{L} \sim 0$ and

$$\Delta_5 \sim \lambda \quad (2.30)$$

About L_{25} we have:

$$\begin{aligned} O'E^2 + O'A^2 &= AE^2 \\ (2L + \lambda)^2 + (L - \lambda)^2 &= \hat{L}_{25}^2 \\ \hat{L}_{25}^2 &= 4L^2 + 4L\lambda + \lambda^2 + L^2 - 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 \\ \hat{L}_{25}^2 &= 5L^2 + 2L\lambda + \lambda^2 \\ \hat{L}_{25} &= \sqrt{5L^2 + 2L\lambda + \lambda^2} \\ \hat{L}_{25} &= \sqrt{5L^2 \left(1 + \frac{2L\lambda}{5L^2} + \frac{\lambda^2}{5L^2}\right)} \\ \hat{L}_{25} &= \sqrt{5L^2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2}{5}\frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{1}{5}\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \\ \hat{L}_{25} &= \sqrt{5}L \sqrt{1 + \frac{2}{5}\frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{1}{5}\frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \end{aligned}$$

But $L_{25} = \sqrt{5}L$, therefore we have:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{L}_{25} &= L_{25} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2}{5} \frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{1}{5} \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2}} \\ \hat{L}_{25} &\sim L_{25} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{5} \frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{1}{5} \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2} \right) \right] \\ \hat{L}_{25} &\sim L_{25} + L_{25} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{5} \frac{\lambda}{L} + \frac{1}{5} \frac{\lambda^2}{L^2} \right) \\ \Delta_7 &= \hat{L}_{25} - L_{25} \sim \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{5} \frac{\hat{L}_{25}}{L} \lambda + \frac{\hat{L}_{25}}{L} \frac{\lambda}{L} \right)\end{aligned}$$

Again $\frac{\lambda}{L} \sim 0$ therefore we have:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_7 &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{2}{5} \frac{\hat{L}_{25}}{L} \lambda = \frac{1}{5} \frac{\hat{L}_{25}}{L} \lambda = \frac{1}{5} \frac{\sqrt{5}L}{L} \lambda = \frac{\sqrt{5}}{5} \lambda = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{5}} \\ \Delta_7 &= \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{5}}\end{aligned}\tag{2.31}$$

The remaining beams don't change their length, therefore we have:

$$\Delta_8 = \hat{L}_{34} - L_{34} = 0\tag{2.32}$$

$$\Delta_9 = \hat{L}_{35} - L_{35} = 0\tag{2.33}$$

$$\Delta_{10} = \hat{L}_{36} - L_{36} = 0\tag{2.34}$$

$$\Delta_{11} = \hat{L}_{45} - L_{45} = 0\tag{2.35}$$

$$\Delta_{12} = \hat{L}_{46} - L_{46} = 0\tag{2.36}$$

$$\Delta_{13} = \hat{L}_{56} - L_{56} = 0.\tag{2.37}$$

The next fundamental step is to report all the displacements just calculated and relate them, in a certain way, with matrix A. This is done in table (2.3):

From table (2.3) we see that

$$\Delta_k = -(a_k)^T u \quad k = 1, \dots, m.\tag{2.38}$$

Applying Hooke's law (see equation (2.20)) to every bar of the truss, we have:

$$\frac{f_k}{A_k} = E_k \frac{\Delta_k}{L_k} \quad k = 1, \dots, m.\tag{2.39}$$

Equations (2.38) and (2.39) are now going to be put together to get another matrix equation which, together with equilibrium conditions, will lead to the optimization problem. Instead of section A_k of bar k , one can also consider volume t_k of the same bar and, keeping in mind that

$$t_k = A_k \times L_k,$$

equation (2.39) then becomes

TABLE OF DISPLACEMENTS				
		$u^T = (-\lambda, -\lambda, 0, 0, 0, 0)$		
Bar k	Nodes	Δ_k	$(a_k)^T$	$(a_k)^T u$
1	12	$-\lambda$	0, -1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0	λ
2	13	0	0, 0, -1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0	0
3	14	0	0, 0, 0, 0, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, 0, 0	0
4	16	0	0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, $-\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$, $-\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$	0
5	23	0	$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, 0, 0, 0, 0	0
6	24	0	1, 0, 0, 0, -1, 0, 0, 0	0
7	25	$\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{5}}$	$\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$, $-\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0	$-\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{5}}$
8	34	0	0, 0, 0, 1, 0, -1, 0, 0	0
9	35	0	0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0	0
10	36	0	0, 0, $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, 0, 0, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$	0
11	45	0	0, 0, 0, 0, $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, $-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, 0, 0	0
12	46	0	0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, -1, 0	0
13	56	0	0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, -1	0

Table 2.3: Table of approximated displacements with relative columns of matrix A.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{f_k}{A_k} &= E_k \frac{\Delta_k}{L_k} \\
f_k &= E_k A_k \frac{\Delta_k}{L_k} \\
f_k &= E_k \frac{A_k L_k}{L_k^2} \Delta_k \\
f_k &= E_k \frac{t_k}{L_k^2} \Delta_k \\
k &= 1, \dots, m.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.40}$$

Plugging (2.38) into (2.40) we have

$$f_k = -\frac{E_k}{L_k^2} t_k (a_k)^T u \quad k = 1, \dots, m. \tag{2.41}$$

Now, instead of having m separated scalar equation we'd rather put them all together dealing with only one matrix equation. Since every equation involves a column of matrix A , we construct the following matrix

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{L_1^2}{E_1 t_1} & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & \frac{L_m^2}{E_m t_m} \end{pmatrix}$$

which is diagonal, hence its inverse is just the reciprocal of diagonal elements:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{E_1 t_1}{L_1^2} & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & \frac{E_m t_m}{L_m^2} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{2.42}$$

Note that matrix B contains the coefficients of equations (2.41). Note also that such equations can now be gathered together into the following new matrix equation:

$$f = -B^{-1} A^T u \quad \text{or} \tag{2.43}$$

$$B f = -B B^{-1} A^T u$$

$$B f = -A^T u$$

$$B f + A^T u = 0. \tag{2.44}$$

2.12 The truss is an indeterminate structure

Consider a generic truss structure such as the one depicted in figure 2.14 and imagine to link together all the nodes involved in the structures with

all the possible bars. Since there are n nodes in the structure then $n - 1$ bars will leave from every node and the total number of bars will be

$$\text{Number of bars} = m = \frac{n(n - 1)}{2}.$$

Figure 2.14: An abstract truss.

The unknowns are the internal forces f_i . There is an internal force for every bar therefore the number of unknowns is the number of bars, i.e.

$$\text{Number of unknowns} = m = \frac{n(n - 1)}{2}.$$

We can write two equilibrium equations (one for the x components and another one for the y components) for every node plus two moment equations (referring to two perpendicular axis); then the number of equations is

$$\text{Number of equations} = 2n + 2 = 2(n + 1).$$

Consider again figure 2.14. Here $n = 6$ and

$$m = \frac{n(n - 1)}{2} = \frac{6(6 - 1)}{2} = \frac{6 \times 5}{2} = 3 \times 5 = 15.$$

The number of unknowns is m which is 15 and the number of equations is $2(n + 1) = 2(6 + 1) = 2 \times 7 = 14 < 15$. Therefore the number of equations

is smaller than the number of unknowns and the system of equations $Af + F = 0$ is indeterminate. That's why the truss structure is said to be an *indeterminate structure*.

To solve the problem new equations are introduced. They are equations (2.43) about the Hooke's law. This means to introduce the hypothesis that we are dealing with non rigid bodies but elastic bodies. With this hypothesis we have m unknowns regarding the internal forces f_i ; $2n$ unknowns regarding x and y displacements of every nodes; $2n$ equations from equilibrium conditions plus m new equations from Hooke's law. Therefore

$$\text{Number of unknowns} = \text{number of equations} = m + 2n$$

and the system is no longer indeterminate.

2.13 Compliance of the structure

So far in studying truss structures we have got equilibrium conditions and displacements (supposed to be small) along the beams due to elasticity. The equations which govern such two phenomena apply at every node for equilibrium and at every bar for displacements and they have been put all together into the two following matrix equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} (2.15) & Af + F = 0 \quad \text{equilibrium conditions} \\ (2.44) & Bf + A^T u = 0 \quad \text{internal forces and bar displacements} \end{array} \right.$$

A force times a displacements gives the energy (or work) relative to that displacement. The energy or work is a scalar value and we have m internal forces (one for every bar) and $p \times d$ (the number of free nodes times the dimension degree of the structure) displacements and external forces collected into column vectors f and u and F respectively. Since F and u are both column vectors of the same length $p \times d$, then the quantity

$$\frac{1}{2} F^T u \tag{2.45}$$

is a scalar value. Such a value is also the product of forces times displacements hence is an energy. We refer to this quantity as the *compliance* of the truss. In other words *the truss is at equilibrium, i.e. nodes don't move even though they may be free, but, before reaching equilibrium, small displacements of free nodes occur due elasticity and internal forces along bars. The sum of the products of external forces times associated displacements of nodes on where they apply, gives the compliance, which is the work (or energy) associated to the whole displacements of nodes which have taken place in the structure.*

We now develop some formulas to determine the compliance, starting from our latter equations. From equations (2.43) we have

$$(2.43) \quad f = -B^{-1}A^T u$$

plus, from equation (2.15) we have

$$(2.15) \quad Af + F = 0$$

Starting from (2.15) and using (2.43) in the following steps we have:

$$\begin{aligned} Af + F &= 0 \\ F &= -Af \\ F &= -A(-B^{-1}A^T u) \\ F &= AB^{-1}A^T u \end{aligned} \tag{2.46}$$

The quantity $AB^{-1}A^T$ is called the *stiffness matrix* of the truss:

$$K \triangleq AB^{-1}A^T. \tag{2.47}$$

Equation (2.46) then can be written as

$$F = Ku. \tag{2.48}$$

Finally the compliance of the truss is found to be

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}F^T u &= \frac{1}{2}(Ku)^T u = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T K^T u = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T (AB^{-1}A^T)^T u = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T (A^T)^T (AB^{-1})^T u = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T A (B^{-1})^T A^T = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T AB^{-1}A^T u = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^T Ku \end{aligned} \tag{2.49}$$

Note that, since B^{-1} is diagonal, then $(B^{-1})^T = B^{-1}$.

2.14 Solving the equations and computing the compliance

From (2.48) one can find nodal displacements u as

$$u = K^{-1}F. \quad (2.50)$$

After that the compliance is computed as

$$\frac{1}{2}u^T K u.$$

2.15 Minimizing the compliance: the truss design problem

As mentioned above the compliance is the work performed by the truss to reach equilibrium. The larger is such elastic energy, the more work the truss undergoes under load F . For this reason the compliance must be as small as possible. But this means that *the compliance must be minimized*. Hence this is the case of an *optimization problem*. **This is one of the goals of truss design: minimizing the compliance by choosing suitable volume bars.** Since length of bars are given by the geometry of the problem; this also means that *cross sections* of beams are the only free variables of the optimization problem. In a formal way, we are seeking for a set of volume bars (which are the design variables) $\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ such that satisfy the following optimization problem:

Optimization Problem 1 Minimize the compliance $\frac{1}{2}F^T u$ subject to

- *equilibrium and displacements equations*
- *volume constraints*

This is the object of the next chapters.

Chapter 3

Convex optimization problems

Mathematical programming or *optimization* is that branch of mathematics which tries to find the best solution for a given problem. In other words we want to minimize (or, in the dual case, maximize) a given function $f_0(x)$ which is known as the *cost function* or *objective function*. Together with the cost function $f_0(x)$ certain constraints relative to the nature of the problems arise, leading to an optimization problem.

3.1 Optimization problems

The formal formulation for an optimization problem is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && f_0(x), && x \in \mathbb{R}^n \\ & \text{subject to} && f_i(x) \leq b_i, && i = 1, \dots, m \\ & && h_i(x) = 0, && i = 1, \dots, p \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

3.2 Linear and non-linear problems

A wide class of problems (3.1) is the one having the objective and constraints function *linear*, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(\alpha x + \beta y) &= \alpha f_i(x) + \beta f_i(y) && i = 0, 1, \dots, m \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, \forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}; \\ h_i(\alpha x + \beta y) &= \alpha h_i(x) + \beta h_i(y) && i = 1, \dots, p \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, \forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

Problems with functions respecting equalities (3.2) are called *linear*; otherwise the problem is *non-linear*. If $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R} \quad \alpha + \beta = 1$ and a wide

sense minority relation (\leq) holds instead of equality, then functions $f_i(x)$ are no longer linear but *convex*, i.e.

$$f_i(\alpha x + \beta y) \leq \alpha f_i(x) + \beta f_i(y),$$

$$\forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R} \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha + \beta = 1. \quad (3.3)$$

Convexity is a wide exploited branch of optimization problems and all the problems inside this thesis will be convex optimization problems. Before studying convex problems related to truss structures, some useful features about convexity will be in the following introduced.

3.3 Convex sets

3.3.1 Lines and segments

Given two distinct points $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the expression

$$y = \theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2, \quad (3.4)$$

represents a segment of vertexes x_1 and x_2 if θ varies from 0 to 1. For $\theta = 0$, in fact, we have

$$y = 0 + (1 - 0)x_2 = x_2.$$

For $\theta = 1$, we have

$$y = 1x_1 + (1 - 1)x_2 = x_1 + 0x_2 = x_1$$

For all $\theta \in (0, 1)$ we get intermediate points between x_1 and x_2 . Expression (3.4) can also be put in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2 \\ y &= \theta x_1 + x_2 - \theta x_2 \\ y &= x_2 + \theta(x_1 - x_2) \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

Looking at (3.5) one can achieve the following interpretation: x_2 is the departure point, $x_1 - x_2$ is the distance between the two extreme points and, finally θ represents the fraction of the way from x_2 to x_1 . Note that if $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ than just varying in $[0, 1]$ only, the result is *the line passing through x_1 and x_2* . Such a difference is fundamental for distinguish between affine and convex sets, defined next.

3.3.2 Affine sets

A set $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is *affine* if the **line** passing through any two distinct points x_1 and x_2 both belonging to set C , is fully contained in C . In other words $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is affine when

$$\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2 \in C \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in C \quad \text{and} \quad \forall \theta \in [0, 1].$$

3.3.3 Convex sets

A set $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is *convex* if the **segment** having as vertexes any two distinct points x_1 and x_2 both belonging to set C , is fully contained in C . In other words $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is convex when

$$\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2 \in C \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in C \text{ and } \forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}.$$

3.4 Convex functions

A convex $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is *convex* if **dom** f is convex and if, for all $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbf{dom} f$ and for all $\theta \in [0, 1]$

$$f(\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2) \leq \theta f(x_1) + (1 - \theta)f(x_2). \quad (3.6)$$

From a geometrical point, convexity means that, given points $(x_1, f(x_1))$ and $(x_2, f(x_2))$ then the segment of vertexes x_1 and x_2 is above function $f(x)$ itself.

3.4.1 An example: parabola

In this example we want to analyze the convexity for the family parabolas

$$f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c,$$

with $a \neq 0$ since, if $a = 0$ the parabola reduces to a line. Here **dom** $f = \mathbb{R}$ and so, $\forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\forall \theta \in [0, 1]$ we must have:

$$f(\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2) \leq \theta f(x_1) + (1 - \theta)f(x_2);$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} & a(\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2)^2 + b(\theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2) + c \leq \\ & \quad \theta (ax_1^2 + bx_1 + c) + (1 - \theta) (ax_2^2 + bx_2 + c) \\ a\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2a\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + a(1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2 + b\theta x_1 + b(1 - \theta)x_2 + c & \leq \\ a\theta x_1^2 + b\theta x_1 + c\theta + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 + b(1 - \theta)x_2 + c(1 - \theta) & \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] + c & \leq \\ a\theta x_1^2 + c\theta + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 + c(1 - \theta) & \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] + c & \leq \\ a\theta x_1^2 + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 + c\theta + c(1 - \theta) & \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] + c & \leq \\ a\theta x_1^2 + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 + c\theta + c - c\theta & \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] + c & \leq \\ a\theta x_1^2 + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 + c. & \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] \leq a\theta x_1^2 + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2$$

Note that coefficients b and c have disappeared; this means they can assume every value in \mathbb{R} , i.e. $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$. We still have to determine which values coefficient a may assume to guarantee convexity. This is done in the following steps:

$$\begin{aligned} a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] &\leq a\theta x_1^2 + a(1 - \theta)x_2^2 \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] &\leq a [\theta x_1^2 + (1 - \theta)x_2^2] \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2] - a [\theta x_1^2 + (1 - \theta)x_2^2] &\leq 0 \\ a [\theta^2 x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2 - x_1^2 - (1 - \theta)x_2^2] &\leq 0 \\ a [(\theta^2 - 1)x_1^2 + 2\theta(1 - \theta)x_1 x_2 + (1 - \theta)^2 x_2^2 - (1 - \theta)x_2^2] &\leq 0 \\ a [(\theta + 1)(\theta - 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta(\theta - 1)x_2 x_1 + (\theta - 1)^2 x_2^2 + (\theta - 1)x_2^2] &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Note that all the terms into square brackets have a common factor $(\theta - 1)$. Since $\theta \in [0, 1]$ then $(\theta - 1) \leq 0$. If $\theta - 1 = 0$ (hence $\theta = 1$) we get a trivial case because the inequality immediately holds. Otherwise we can divide by $\theta - 1$ but the inequality changes versus.

$$\begin{aligned} a [(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + (\theta - 1)x_2^2 + x_2^2] &\geq 0 \\ a [(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + (\theta - 1 + 1)x_2^2] &\geq 0 \\ a [(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + \theta x_2^2] &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Imagining to solve equation $(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + \theta x_2^2 = 0$ for x_1 , we get the following reduced discriminant:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta}{4} &= (\theta x_2)^2 - (\theta + 1)(\theta x_2^2) = \\ &= \theta^2 x_2^2 - \theta^2 x_2^2 - \theta x_2^2 = \\ &= -\theta x_2^2 \leq 0, \end{aligned}$$

since $x_2^2 \geq 0$ and $\theta \in [0, 1]$. This means that

$$(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + \theta x_2^2 \geq 0 \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and } \forall \theta \in [0, 1]$$

Since $a [(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + \theta x_2^2]$ must be equal or greater than zero and we have just proved that $[(\theta + 1)x_1^2 - 2\theta x_2 x_1 + \theta x_2^2]$ is already equal or greater than zero, then it follows that, to guarantee convexity it must be

$$a > 0.$$

Note that, as observed before, if $a = 0$ the parabola reduces to a line and convexity (3.6) holds as an equality which further means we are in the linearity case. This also means that linearity is a particular case of convexity.

Figure 3.1: Geometrical meaning of convexity.

Figure 3.1 shows the geometrical meaning of convexity. Here $f(x)$ is the parabola $y = \frac{1}{2}x^2$.

The next pages are devoted to some useful theorems which characterize convex functions. The proofs of such theorems can also be found in [7], [16] and [15]. The first theorem gives a condition to check whether a function f is convex or not.

Theorem 1 Let $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be a function with **dom** f convex. Given two points $x, y \in \mathbf{dom} f$ and a function $g_{xy}(\theta) : [0, 1] \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ with $g_{xy}(\theta) = f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x)$, then function f is convex if and only if¹ g_{xy} is convex for all x, y in **dom** f .

Proof The first part of the proof demonstrates that, if f is convex then there is a function g_{xy} with the characteristics stated in the theorem. To do so consider two numbers $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and a third number $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and consider θ as follows

$$\theta = \lambda\alpha + (1 - \lambda)\beta$$

By construction $\theta \in [0, 1]$. We also have that

¹if and only if is abbreviated as *iif* or as \iff .

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{xy}(\theta) &= g_{xy}(\lambda\alpha + (1-\lambda)\beta) = & (3.7) \\
&= f(\theta y + (1-\theta)x) = \\
&= f((\lambda\alpha + (1-\lambda)\beta)y + (1 - (\lambda\alpha + (1-\lambda)\beta))x) = \\
&= f(\lambda\alpha y + (1-\lambda)\beta y + x - \lambda\alpha x - (1-\lambda)\beta x) = \\
&= f(\lambda(\alpha y - \alpha x) + (1-\lambda)(\beta y - \beta x) + x) & (3.8)
\end{aligned}$$

If one expresses the last x appearing in (3.8) as

$$x = x(1 - \lambda + \lambda) = (1 - \lambda)x + \lambda x$$

then it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{xy}(\theta) &= g_{xy}(\lambda\alpha + (1-\lambda)\beta) = \\
&= f(\lambda(\alpha y - \alpha x) + (1-\lambda)(\beta y - \beta x) + x) = \\
&= f(\lambda(\alpha y - \alpha x) + (1-\lambda)(\beta y - \beta x) + (1-\lambda)x + \lambda x) = \\
&= f(\lambda(\alpha y - \alpha x + x) + (1-\lambda)(\beta y - \beta x + x)) = \\
&= f(\lambda(\alpha y + (1-\alpha)x) + (1-\lambda)(\beta y + (1-\beta)x)) \leq \quad \text{since } f \text{ in convex} \\
&\leq \lambda f(\alpha y + (1-\alpha)x) + (1-\lambda)f(\beta y + (1-\beta)x) = \\
&= \lambda g_{xy}(\alpha) + (1-\lambda)g_{xy}(\beta).
\end{aligned}$$

This concludes the first part of the proof. The second part consists of proving that f is convex if g_{xy} is convex. To do so, note that, since

$$g_{xy}(\theta) = f(\theta y + (1-\theta)x),$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{xy}(0) &= f(0y + (1-0)x) = f(0y + 1x) = f(x) \\
g_{xy}(1) &= f(1y + (1-1)x) = f(1y - 0x) = f(y)
\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
f(\theta y + (1-\theta)x) &= g_{xy}(\theta) = \\
&= g_{xy}(\theta \cdot 1 + (1-\theta) \cdot 0) \leq \quad \text{since } g_{xy} \text{ is convex} \\
&\leq \theta g_{xy}(1) + (1-\theta)g_{xy}(0) = \\
&= \theta f(y) + (1-\theta)f(x).
\end{aligned}$$

♣

The worth of this theorem is that convexity condition on f is restricted to a line g_{xy} . Theorem (1) will be useful for the next theorem which gives first order condition about convexity. Before stating and proving the theorem one must recall the meaning of differentiability.

3.4.2 Differentiable functions

A function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is differentiable if its gradient

$$\nabla f = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_n} \right)^T$$

exists at each point in $\mathbf{dom} f$ which is open and the partial derivatives are continuous in $\mathbf{dom} f$.

Theorem 2 (First order conditions) *Let $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function. Then f is convex if and only if $\mathbf{dom} f$ is convex and, for all $x, y \in \mathbf{dom} f$ the following inequality holds:*

$$f(y) \geq f(x) + \nabla f(x)^T (y - x). \quad (3.9)$$

Proof Note that, if $x = y$ thesis trivially holds, thus, beyond this point, we'll suppose $x \neq y$. We first demonstrate the theorem for the monodimensional case (i.e. $n = 1$) and then, thanks to theorem 1, we'll apply it to the general case.

Monodimensional case We prove this part of the theorem in two steps: first we show that if f is convex then (3.9) holds and then we'll prove the inverse proposition: if (3.9) holds then f must be convex. Note that in the monodimensional case $\mathbf{dom} f$ reduces to an open interval. Choose two distinct points x, y belonging to such interval. Since f is convex then even $\mathbf{dom} f$ must be convex hence, for all $\theta \in [0, 1]$

$$\theta y + (1 - \theta)x \in \mathbf{dom} f$$

Let $\theta \rightarrow 0$ (thus we can divide by θ), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x) &\leq \theta f(y) + (1 - \theta)f(x) \\ f(\theta y + x - \theta x) &\leq \theta f(y) + f(x) - \theta f(x) \\ f(x + \theta(y - x)) &\leq \theta(f(y) - f(x)) + f(x) \\ f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x) &\leq \theta(f(y) - f(x)) \\ \frac{f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x)}{\theta} &\leq f(y) - f(x) \\ f(x) + \frac{f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x)}{\theta} &\leq f(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(y) &\geq f(x) + \frac{f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x)}{\theta} \\ f(y) &\geq f(x) + \frac{f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x)}{\theta} \cdot \frac{y - x}{y - x} \quad \text{since } x \neq y \\ f(y) &\geq f(x) + \frac{f(x + \theta(y - x)) - f(x)}{\theta(y - x)} (y - x) \end{aligned}$$

Note that if $\theta \rightarrow 0$ also $\theta(y-x)$ does. Taking the limit for $\theta \rightarrow 0$ and considering the substitution

$$h \triangleq \theta(y-x)$$

we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} f(y) &\geq \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \left(f(x) + \frac{f(x + \theta(y-x)) - f(x)}{\theta(y-x)} (y-x) \right) \\ f(y) &\geq f(x) + \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x + \theta(y-x)) - f(x)}{\theta(y-x)} (y-x) \\ f(y) &\geq f(x) + \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h} (y-x) \\ f(y) &\geq f(x) + f'(x) (y-x). \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Let us now prove that, if (3.10) holds then f is convex. To do so consider

$$z \triangleq \theta x + (1-\theta)y, \quad \theta \in [0, 1]$$

and evaluate (3.10) in $x = z$ then we have

$$f(y) \geq f(z) + f'(z) (y-z). \quad (3.11)$$

Evaluating (3.11) for $y = x$ we also have

$$f(x) \geq f(z) + f'(z) (x-z). \quad (3.12)$$

Multiplying (3.11) by $(1-\theta)$ and (3.12) by θ we get

$$(1-\theta) f(y) \geq (1-\theta) f(z) + (1-\theta) f'(z) (y-z) \quad (3.13)$$

$$\theta f(x) \geq \theta f(z) + \theta f'(z) (x-z) \quad (3.14)$$

Summing (3.13) and (3.14) we have

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\theta) f(y) + \theta f(x) &\geq (1-\theta) f(z) + \theta f(z) + (1-\theta) f'(z) (y-z) + \theta f'(z) (x-z) \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [(1-\theta)(y-z) + \theta(x-z)] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [y-z - \theta y + \theta z + \theta x - \theta z] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [y-z - \theta y + \theta x] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [\theta x + (1-\theta)y - z] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [z-z] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) + f'(z) [0] \\ \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y) &\geq f(z) \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

Since $z = \theta x + (1-\theta)y$, (3.15) yields to

$$f(\theta x + (1-\theta)y) \leq \theta f(x) + (1-\theta) f(y)$$

which proves convexity and also concludes the first part of the theorem.

Multidimensional case

For the multidimensional case we use the result of theorem 1, i.e. given two distinct points $x, y \in \mathbf{dom} f$ and for all $\theta \in [0, 1]$ it is enough to restrict function f considering it with the line passing through x and y only. This is done considering the function

$$g_{xy}(\theta) = f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x), \quad \theta \in [0, 1].$$

Remind that $g_{xy}(0) = f(x)$ and $g_{xy}(1) = f(y)$. We first prove that, if f is convex then (3.9) holds.

$$g'_{xy}(\theta) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x) = \nabla f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x)^T \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\theta y + (1 - \theta)x) = \nabla f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x)^T (y - x)$$

For theorem 1 if f is convex even g_{xy} is. But, since g_{xy} is convex and monodimensional, for the first part of this theorem it satisfies (3.10), i.e.

$$g_{xy}(\theta_1) \geq g_{xy}(\theta_2) + f'(\theta_2)(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \quad \forall \theta_1, \theta_2 \in [0, 1].$$

Putting all together these items of information we can write

$$f(y) = g_{xy}(1) \geq g_{xy}(0) + g'_{xy}(0)(1 - 0) = g_{xy}(0) + g'_{xy}(0) = f(x) + \nabla f(x)^T (y - x), \quad \text{i.e.}$$

$$f(y) \geq f(x) + \nabla f(x)^T (y - x).$$

The last part of the theorem consists in proving that, if (3.9) holds then f is convex. To do so consider $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $x_1 \triangleq \alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x \in \mathbf{dom} f$ and $x_2 \triangleq \beta y + (1 - \beta)x \in \mathbf{dom} f$. Due to (3.9) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} f(x_1) &\geq f(x_2) + \nabla f(x_2)^T (x_1 - x_2) \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T [(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) - (\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)] \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T [\alpha y + x - \alpha x - \beta y - x + \beta x] \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T [\alpha y - \alpha x - \beta y + \beta x] \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T [(\alpha - \beta)y - (\alpha - \beta)x] \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T [(\alpha - \beta)(y - x)] \\ f(\alpha y + (1 - \alpha)x) &\geq f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T (y - x) (\alpha - \beta) \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Defining, as always, $g_{xy}(\theta) \triangleq f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x)$, (3.16) states that

$$\begin{aligned} g_{xy}(\alpha) &\geq g_{xy}(\beta) + \nabla f(\beta y + (1 - \beta)x)^T (y - x) (\alpha - \beta) = \\ &= g_{xy}(\beta) + g'_{xy}(\beta) (\alpha - \beta), \quad \text{i.e.} \\ g_{xy}(\alpha) &\geq g_{xy}(\beta) + g'_{xy}(\beta) (\alpha - \beta), \end{aligned}$$

which is (3.10). This involves that $g_{xy}(\theta)$ is convex; but, due to theorem 1, this implies that f is convex.

Note that $f(x) + \nabla f(x)^T(y - x)$ is the first order Taylor approximation of f near x . Theorem 2 hence means that if the first order Taylor approximation is always a global underestimator of f then f is convex. Inequality (3.10) also means that from a local information about a convex function (its value and gradient at a point) we can a global information (a global underestimator of it). This concept is also shown in figure 3.2 which shows parabola of equation $y = \frac{1}{4}x^2$.

Figure 3.2: Graphical meaning of theorem 2.

3.4.3 Twice differentiable functions

A function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is twice differentiable if its *Hessian*

$$\nabla^2 f(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_1 \partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_2 \partial x_1} & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_2^2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_2 \partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_n \partial x_1} & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_n \partial x_2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_n^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

exists at each point in $\text{dom } f$, which is open and its partial derivatives are continuous.

The following theorem gives second order condition for convexity of function f .

Theorem 3 (Second order conditions) *Let $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be twice differentiable; then f is convex if and only if $\mathbf{dom} f$ is convex and $\nabla^2 f(x)$ is positive semidefinite for all $x \in \mathbf{dom} f$, i.e.*

$$\nabla^2 f(x) \succeq 0 \tag{3.17}$$

Notice that, when $n = 1$, (3.17) reduces to the well known condition

$$f''(x) \geq 0.$$

3.5 The concept of epigraph

Consider a function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$; then its graph is defined as

$$\mathbf{graph} f = \{(x, f(x)) \mid x \in \mathbf{dom} f\},$$

which is a subset of \mathbb{R}^{n+1} . In a similar way the concept of epigraph is defined: whilst $\mathbf{graph} f$ is the set of points *of* the function itself, $\mathbf{epi} f$ is the set of points *above* the function (greek prefix *epi* means, in fact, *above*):

$$\mathbf{epi} f = \{(x, t) \mid x \in \mathbf{dom} f \text{ and } f(x) \leq t\},$$

which is a subset of \mathbb{R}^{n+1} . Figure 3.3 illustrates the difference between graph and epigraph.

The concept of epigraph is important because, as it will be shown later, robust problem of the form

$$\min_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \max_{\delta \in \Delta} f(x, \delta)$$

can be stated in the following epigraphic form:

$$\min_{t, x \in \mathcal{X}} t \quad \text{subject to} \quad f(x, \delta) \leq t \quad \forall \delta \in \Delta.$$

3.6 Introduction to convex optimization problems

An optimization problem in standard form can be stated as

Convex Optimization Problem 1

$$\begin{aligned} \min & f(x) \\ \text{subject to} & g_i(x) \leq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, m \\ & h_i(x) = 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, p; \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.3: Difference between graph and epigraph.

where functions f and g_i are defined, convex and differentiable over a convex open set \mathcal{D} which is the intersection of all the single domains of every function; i.e.

$$\mathcal{D} = \mathbf{dom} f \cap \left(\bigcap_{i=1}^m \mathbf{dom} g_i \right);$$

and functions h_i are affine of the form

$$h_i(x) = (a^i)^T x - b_i;$$

with $a^i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $b_i \in \mathbb{R}$.

A point x such that it respects all the constraints of convex optimization problem 1 is said to be an *acceptable point* of the problem. We define set X as the set of all the acceptable points. Every next sections shows features of convex optimization problem 1 provided that certain conditions are satisfied.

3.6.1 The dual problem

Consider a similar optimization problem (this times not convex for a straightforward reason which will be clear very soon) as follows:

Optimization Problem 2

$$\begin{aligned} & \max && f(x) \\ \text{subject to} && g_i(x) \leq 0 && i = 1, \dots, m \\ && h_i(x) = 0 && i = 1, \dots, p; \end{aligned}$$

with $f(x)$ concave and all the functions having the same features of convex optimization problem 1. But

$$\max\{f(x) : x \in \mathcal{D}\} = -\min\{-f(x) : x \in \mathcal{D}\}$$

therefore the problem of maximizing a concave problem over an open and convex set \mathcal{D} is equivalent to convex optimization 1 with just two changes of signs. This result is known as *duality*.

3.6.2 Optima of the problem

x^* is a *global optimum* (or simply an *optimum*) if $x \in X$ and $f(x^*) \leq f(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

x^* is a *local optimum* if $x \in X$ and there exists $R > 0$ such that x^* is a global optimum for the problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \min && f(x) && (3.18) \\ \text{subject to} && g_i(x) \leq 0 && i = 1, \dots, m \\ && h_i(x) = 0 && i = 1, \dots, p \\ && \|x - x^*\| \leq R && (3.19) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4 *If x^* is a local optimum for convex optimization problem 1 then x^* is also a global optimum.*

Proof If x^* is a local optimum, then there exists a $R > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \min && f(x) \\ \text{subject to} && g_i(x) \leq 0 && i = 1, \dots, m \\ && h_i(x) = 0 && i = 1, \dots, p \\ && \|x - x^*\| \leq R \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that x^* is *not* a global optimum but just a local one. Then there exist y outside $\mathcal{B}(x^*, R)$, i.e. $\|y - x^*\| > R$, such that $f(y) < f(x^*)$. Consider θ defined as follows:

$$\theta = \frac{R}{2\|y - x^*\|}.$$

Since $\|y - x^*\| > R$ then

$$\theta = \frac{R}{2\|y - x^*\|} < \frac{R}{2R} < \frac{1}{2} < 1.$$

Note also that, by construction, $\theta > 0$ hence

$$0 < \theta < 1$$

and the following point

$$z = \theta y + (1 - \theta)x^*$$

is feasible, due to convexity of the feasible set. With some calculus we get

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \theta y + (1 - \theta)x^* \\ z &= \theta y + x^* - \theta x^* \\ z - x^* &= \theta y - \theta x^* \\ z - x^* &= \theta(y - x^*) \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \|z - x^*\| &= \|\theta(y - x^*)\| = \\ &= |\theta| \|y - x^*\| = \\ &= \theta \|y - x^*\| = \\ &= \frac{R}{2\|y - x^*\|} \|y - x^*\| = \\ &= \frac{R}{2} < R, \end{aligned}$$

hence $z \in \mathcal{B}(x^*, R)$ and, since x^* is a local optimum, then

$$f(z) \geq f(x^*) \tag{3.20}$$

Since we are supposing that $f(y) < f(x^*)$, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) &= f(\theta y + (1 - \theta)x^*) \leq \\ &\leq \theta f(y) + (1 - \theta)f(x^*) < \\ &< \theta f(x^*) + (1 - \theta)f(x^*) = \\ &= (\theta + 1 - \theta)f(x^*) = f(x^*), \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts (3.20). It follows that x^* is a *global* optimum.

In a similar way the following theorem can be proven:

Theorem 5 *If x^* is a local optimum of problem (1); if f is strictly convex then x^* is the only optimum of the problem.*

3.6.3 The unconstrained problem

In this section we want to provide conditions that guarantee the existence of optima points. Let's start with the easiest case which is the problem without constraints:

Convex Optimization Problem 2

$$\min f(x)$$

Consider again first order conditions of theorem 2:

$$f(y) \geq f(x) + \nabla f(x)^T(y - x);$$

then if there exist a point $x \in \mathcal{D}$ such that $\nabla f(x) = 0$ then it follows that, for all $y \in \mathcal{D}$

$$f(y) \geq f(x);$$

which means that x is a global optimum. Therefore

$$\nabla f(x) = 0$$

is a sufficient condition for optima existence for unconstrained convex problems.

3.6.4 The convex optimization problem with equality constraints only

By generalizing unconstrained problem 2 to the same problem this time having also equality constraints we then need to find optima conditions for the following problem:

Convex Optimization Problem 3

$$\begin{aligned} \min & f(x) \\ \text{subject to} & h_i(x) = 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, p. \end{aligned}$$

We suppose that for all $x \in X$ the gradient of f can be expressed as a linear combination of the gradients of the equality constraints; i.e.

$$\nabla f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i \nabla h_i(x); \tag{3.21}$$

with $\nu \in \mathbb{R}^p$. Let x^* be another acceptable point then ν^* will be its associated coefficient of expression (3.21). Since $h_i(x) = 0$ we can write that

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i h_i(x) = 0;$$

But then we also have that

$$f(x) = f(x) - 0 = f(x) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i h_i(x). \quad (3.22)$$

Using (3.22) into first order conditions with point x and x^* we get the following result:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &\geq f(x^*) + \nabla f(x^*)^T (x - x^*) \\ f(x) &\geq \left(f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*) \right) + \nabla \left(f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*) \right)^T (x - x^*) \end{aligned}$$

Since h_i are affine we can perform the following step:

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*) + \left(\nabla f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* \nabla h_i(x^*) \right)^T (x - x^*)$$

But $\nabla f(x^*) = \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* \nabla h_i(x^*)$ therefore we get:

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* \nabla h_i(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* \nabla h_i(x^*) \right)^T (x - x^*);$$

then

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*);$$

but, again, $\sum_{i=1}^p \nu_i^* h_i(x^*) = 0$ hence we have

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*)$$

which means that x^* is an optimum. Therefore condition (3.21) is sufficient for optimum existence. Coefficients ν are called *Lagrange multipliers*.

3.6.5 The general problem: Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions

Before proceeding we give a new definition: a constraint $g_i(x) \leq 0$ is said to be *active* at acceptable point \bar{x} if $g_i(\bar{x}) = 0$; otherwise it is said to be *inactive*. For the general problem we suppose that the gradient of f can be expressed as a linear combination of constraints g_i and h_j and that only active points can have positive Lagrange multipliers (complementary conditions); i.e.

Convex Optimization Problem 4

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f(x) \quad \text{subject to} \\ & g_i(x) \leq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, m \\ & h_i(x) = 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, p; \\ & \nabla f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \nabla g_i(x) + \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j \nabla h_j(x) \\ & \lambda_i \geq 0 \\ & \lambda_i \text{ are positive for active points } x \text{ where} \\ & \lambda_i g_i(x) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

These conditions are known as Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions (KKT) and the next theorem proves that they are sufficient for optimum existence.

Theorem 6 *Let $(x^*, \lambda^*, \nu^*) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^p$ a solution of convex optimization problem 4 with Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions; then x^* is a global optimum for of the problem.*

Proof In fact, since

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i g_i(x) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j h_j(x) = 0,$$

we can write

$$f(x) = f(x) - 0 - 0 = f(x) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i g_i(x) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j h_j(x);$$

and using first order conditions with points x and x^* we have that

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &\geq f(x^*) + \nabla f(x^*)^T (x - x^*) \\ f(x) &\geq \left(f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* g_i^*(x) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* h_j^*(x^*) \right) + \nabla \left(f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* g_i^*(x) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* h_j^*(x^*) \right)^T (x - x^*) \end{aligned}$$

Since functions g_i are differentiable and h_i are affine we can write

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* g_i^*(x^*) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* h_j(x^*) + \left(\nabla f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* \nabla g_i^*(x^*) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* \nabla h_j(x^*) \right)^T (x - x^*)$$

But, by hypothesis,

$$\nabla f(x^*) = \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* \nabla g_i(x^*) + \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* \nabla h_j(x^*)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* \nabla g_i^*(x^*) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* \nabla h_j(x^*) &= \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* \nabla g_i(x^*) + \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* \nabla h_j(x^*) + \\ &\quad - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* \nabla g_i^*(x^*) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* \nabla h_j(x^*) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

and we just have

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^* g_i^*(x^*) - \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j^* h_j(x^*).$$

But $h_j(x^*) = 0$ and, by hypothesis $\lambda_i^* g_i^*(x^*) = 0$ therefore

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*)$$

and x^* is a global optimum.

It can be proven that KKT conditions are also necessary if other conditions are satisfied. These new conditions are known as *Slater* conditions which can be found in [7], [15] and [16].

All these tools about convex optimization are now going to be applied to the truss structure design: this is the goal of the next chapter.

3.7 LMI problems

This section wants to be a rough introduction to LMI problems. LMI stands for *Linear Matrix Inequalities*. Its formulation will be exploited in the next chapter when we will be talking about the Schur complement. A linear matrix inequality has the form of

$$F(x) \triangleq F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_k F_k \succ 0; \quad (3.23)$$

with $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $F_k \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \forall k = 0, 1, \dots, m$ symmetric. The symbol \succ stands for *positive definite* which means that, for every vector $x \in \mathbb{F}^n$ then

$$x^* F x > 0.$$

A positive definite matrix is characterized by having positive eigenvalues; in fact, for every eigenvalue λ_i with corresponding eigenvector \mathbf{u}_i we have

$$\mathbf{u}_i^* F \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{u}_i^* \lambda \mathbf{u}_i = \lambda \mathbf{u}_i^* \mathbf{u}_i = \lambda \|\mathbf{u}_i\|^2 > 0;$$

therefore all the eigenvalues λ must be positive. Analogous considerations hold for positive semidefinite (i.e. $x^* F x \geq 0$), negative definite and negative semidefinite matrices.

Hence the problem consists in determining the set X of acceptable points such that (3.23) is satisfied.

Linear Matrix Inequalities may appear as constraints in convex optimization problems; formally we can write

Convex Optimization Problem 5 (with LMI constraints)

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f(x) \quad \text{subject to} \\ & f(x) \text{ is convex and} \\ & F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_k F_k \succ 0. \end{aligned}$$

Of course $f(x)$ is convex if we are dealing with convex optimization problems, but how about set X of acceptable points x ? We know that, in order to exploit convex optimization results, set X must be convex. We want to show in the next theorem that that is the case (see, for instance, [17, page 36]).

Theorem 7 *The set X of acceptable points of the LMI constraint $F(x) = F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_k F_k \succ 0$ is convex.*

Proof In fact, for any $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ and for any $x_1, x_2 \in X$ we build vector $v = \theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2$. Since x_1 and x_2 are acceptable points for the constraint and $F(x) \succ 0$ then we both have that

$$F(x_1) = F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_{1,k} F_k \succ 0$$

and

$$F(x_2) = F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_{2,k} F_k \succ 0.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
F(v) &= F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m v_{1,k} F_k = \\
&= F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m (\theta x_{1,k} + (1-\theta)x_{2,k}) F_k = \\
&= \theta F_0 + (1-\theta)F_0 + \theta \sum_{k=1}^m x_{1,k} F_k + (1-\theta) \sum_{k=1}^m x_{2,k} F_k = \\
&= \theta \left(F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_{1,k} F_k \right) + (1-\theta) \left(F_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m x_{2,k} F_k \right) = \\
&= \theta F(x_1) + (1-\theta)F(x_2) \succ 0.
\end{aligned}$$

♣

Perhaps the most powerful property of LMI theory is that to transform a set of nonlinear matrix inequalities into an LMI problem. It will be proved in the next chapter that the nonlinear matrix inequalities

$$A(x) \succ 0 \quad \text{and} \quad C(x) - B^*(x)A(x)^{-1}B(x)$$

is equivalent to the LMI problem

$$\begin{bmatrix} A(x) & B(x) \\ B^*(x) & C(x) \end{bmatrix} \succ 0.$$

This property is called the Schur complement and it will be one of the goals of the next chapter. For further information about LMI problems see [8].

Chapter 4

Convex optimization applied to truss structures: truss design techniques

So far physical laws associated to truss structures and convex optimization characterizations have been shown. In this chapter we want to go back to problem 3 at the end of chapter one and give rise to new equivalent and more specialized optimization problems through the use of a new instrument: the Schur complement.

4.1 Viewing the equilibrium conditions as the solution of an optimization problem

At the end of chapter one we wrote the following optimization problem:

Optimization Problem 3 *Minimize the compliance $\frac{1}{2}F^T u$ subject to*

- *equilibrium and displacements equations*
- *volume constraints;*

where the equilibrium and displacements equations are

$$Af + F = 0$$

$$Bf + A^T u = 0.$$

We now want to show in a more formal way that the truss system is nature's solution to an optimization problem. Consider, in fact, the following optimization problem:

Optimization Problem 4

$$\min_{\tilde{f}} \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2 \quad \text{subject to}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^m a_k \tilde{f}_k = -F;$$

where a_k are column vectors. We are now ready to apply Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions to optimization problem 4. Here \tilde{f} plays the role of x , $\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2$ plays the role of $f(x)$ and $\sum_{k=1}^m a_k \tilde{f}_k + F$ plays the role of $h_i(x)$.

$$\nabla f(x) = \sum_{k=1}^m \nu_k \nabla h_k(x)$$

means

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k = \sum_{k=1}^m a_k^T \nu$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k - \sum_{k=1}^m a_k^T \nu = 0$$

Let now $\nu = -u$ then we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k + \sum_{k=1}^m a_k^T u = 0$$

which can be gathered into matrix form

$$Bf + A^T u = 0$$

which are just the displacements equations with $(b_k) = \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k}$. Note also that the constraint

$$\sum_{k=1}^m a_k \tilde{f}_k = -F$$

in matrix form is $Af = -F$ or $Af + F = 0$ which are equilibrium conditions.

Furthermore, since $(b_k) = \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k}$ we have that

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2 = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \tilde{f}_k (b_k) \tilde{f}_k = \frac{1}{2} f^T Bf.$$

But, from $Bf + A^T u = 0$ we have $Bf = -A^T u$ hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2 = -\frac{1}{2} f^T A^T u.$$

Since the cost function is a scalar then it is even equal to its transpose; therefore we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2 = -\frac{1}{2} f^T A^T u = \frac{1}{2} (f^T A^T u)^T = -\frac{1}{2} u^T A f = -\frac{1}{2} u^T (-F) = \frac{1}{2} u^T F.$$

Again $u^T F$ is a scalar and therefore it is equal to its transpose; hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{t_k} \frac{L_k^2}{E_k} \tilde{f}_k^2 = \frac{1}{2} F^T u$$

which is the compliance. Therefore we see, in a more formal way, that the object function of the optimization problem is the compliance of the truss system.

The truss design problem can then also be formalized by joining equilibrium and displacements conditions into the stiffness matrix equation (as shown at chapter two) to come to the following optimization problem:

Optimization Problem 5

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{t, u} \quad & \frac{1}{2} F^T u \quad \text{subject to} \\ & K(t)u = F \\ & \text{and volume constraints.} \end{aligned}$$

Note that, as written, problem 5 is not convex since, in general, variables t and u are multiplied together in the matrix constraints equation. The next chapter shows how to convert it into a convex problem.

4.2 Towards the truss design convex optimization problem

Consider again equation (2.49) where the compliance $\frac{1}{2} F^T u$ has been written as

$$\frac{1}{2} u^T K u$$

Problem 3 can also be written as

Optimization Problem 6

$$\min_t \frac{1}{2} u^T K(t) u \quad \text{subject to}$$

various constraints.

Problem 6 can also be written in epigraphical form

Optimization Problem 7 (epigraphical form)

$$\min_t \Gamma \quad \text{subject to}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} u^T K(t) u \leq \Gamma$$

and various constraints.

Since $F = K(t)u$ then $u = K^{-1}(t)F$ so

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} u^T K(t) u &= \frac{1}{2} (K^{-1}(t)F)^T K(t) (K^{-1}(t)F) = \frac{1}{2} \left(F^T (K^{-1}(t))^T \right) K(t) K^{-1}(t) F = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} F^T (K(t)^{-1})^T F. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

Remember from (2.47) that

$$K = AB^{-1}A^T.$$

Since B^{-1} is diagonal then $(B^{-1})^T = B^{-1}$ and we have

$$K^{-1} = (A^T)^{-1} (AB^{-1})^{-1} = (A^T)^{-1} (B^{-1})^{-1} A^{-1} = (A^T)^{-1} BA^{-1} = (A^{-1})^T BA^{-1}$$

and¹

$$\begin{aligned} (K(t)^{-1})^T &= \left((A^{-1})^T BA^{-1} \right)^T = (A^{-1})^T \left((A^{-1})^T B \right)^T = \\ &= (A^{-1})^T B^T \left((A^{-1})^T \right)^T = (A^{-1})^T B^T A^{-1} = K(t)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(K(t)^{-1})^T = K(t)^{-1}$ and (4.1) becomes

¹Observe that we have used the property that, given a nonsingular matrix A then $(A^{-1})^T = (A^T)^{-1}$. In some texts such commutative property is condensed into the notation A^{-T} .

$$\frac{1}{2}u^T K(t)u = \frac{1}{2}F^T (K(t)^{-1})^T F = \frac{1}{2}F^T K(t)^{-1}F.$$

Observe that $\frac{1}{2}F^T K(t)^{-1}F \leq \Gamma$ is equivalent to $F^T K(t)^{-1}F \leq 2\Gamma$. Now introducing a new variable γ such that $\gamma = \Gamma$ then, without altering the solution which we wish to find, problem 7 becomes

Optimization Problem 8 (epigraphical form)

$$\begin{aligned} \min_t \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & F^T K(t)^{-1}F \leq \gamma \\ & \text{and various constraints.} \end{aligned}$$

Here comes the key step which transforms problem 8 into a LMI problem. To do so we express inequality

$$F^T K(t)^{-1}F \leq \gamma$$

as

$$\gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1}F \geq 0 \tag{4.2}$$

Inequality (4.2) can be seen as a positive semidefinite *complement of Schur*. The next section defines and deals with complements of Schur. With the results which are going to be expressed, it will be possible transform problem 8 into an LMI problem.

4.3 Gaussian elimination and the Schur complement

To show the origin of the Schur complement² consider to solve an $n \times n$ homogeneous system $Mz = 0$ of linear equations through Gaussian elimination³. Here

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} a & b^T \\ c & D \end{bmatrix}.$$

and the (1, 1) entry a is nonzero. In case $a = 0$ it is possible to swap the first row of M with another line - say line k - such that entry $(k, 1)$ is nonzero and redefine matrix M . Since a is a scalar and the order of matrix M is n

²A very detailed book on the Schur complement is [34].

³Appendix A shows a brief review on Gaussian elimination and gives the basic linear algebra tools to undergo this section.

it easily follows that D is a square $n - 1$ matrix and b and c are columns vectors of size $n - 1$ (therefore b^T is a row vector of size $n - 1$). Partition the unknown vector as follows:

$$z = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } x \in \mathbb{F} \quad \text{and } y \in \mathbb{F}^{(n-1) \times 1}.$$

Therefore we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b^T \\ c & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Starting from matrix M

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b^T \\ c & D \end{bmatrix}.$$

Since $a \neq 0$ there exist a^{-1} and if we sum the second row to the first row multiplied by $-ca^{-1}$ we get the equivalent matrix⁴

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b^T \\ \mathbf{0} & D - ca^{-1}b^T \end{bmatrix}$$

and the original system reduces to

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b^T \\ \mathbf{0} & D - ca^{-1}b^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Since $D - ca^{-1}b^T$ is a $n - 1$ square block; now the problem is to solve, with the same technique, a new reduced system. This iterative way to proceed is called *Gaussian elimination* and the final form is like the one shown in (B.2) or (B.3). The same philosophy can be extended to matrices having as (1, 1) entry a nonsingular matrix A instead a scalar value a , i.e. M is partitioned as follows:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{bmatrix};$$

with $z = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}$ partitioned conformally with M . The associated linear homogeneous system is

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Since A is nonsingular then A^{-1} exists and we can perform operation $R_2 - CA^{-1}R_1$ to get

⁴By denoting with R_1 the first row and with R_2 the second block of row; then this means that we are performing $R_2 - ca^{-1}R_1$.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ \mathbf{0} & D - CA^{-1}B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}.$$

This means that the original homogeneous linear system has reduced to another of smaller sizes. Such a system is

$$(D - CA^{-1}B) = 0.$$

The matrix $D - CA^{-1}B$ is called *the Schur complement of A in M* or *the Schur complement of M relative to A* and is denoted as M/A

$$M/A = D - CA^{-1}B.$$

The Schur complement can also be defined relative to B , C and D as long as such matrices are nonsingular. For instance the Schur complement of D in M is

$$M/D = A - BD^{-1}C.$$

Schur complements also appear in linear nonhomogeneous system as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \end{bmatrix};$$

$$R_2 - CA^{-1}R_1$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ \mathbf{0} & D - CA^{-1}B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v - CA^{-1}u \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ \mathbf{0} & M/A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v - CA^{-1}u \end{bmatrix};$$

$$R_1 - B(M/A)^{-1}R_2$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & M/A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u - B(M/A)^{-1}(v - CA^{-1}u) \\ v - CA^{-1}Bu \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\begin{cases} x = A^{-1}(u - B(M/A)^{-1}(v - CA^{-1}u)) \\ y = (M/A)^{-1}(v - CA^{-1}u) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} x = A^{-1}(u - B(M/A)^{-1}v + B(M/A)^{-1}CA^{-1}u) \\ y = (M/A)^{-1}(v - CA^{-1}u) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} x &= A^{-1} \left((I + B(M/A)^{-1}CA^{-1}) u - B(M/A)^{-1}v \right) \\ y &= (M/A)^{-1} (v - CA^{-1}u) \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

In (4.3) solution vectors x and y are expressed in terms of Schur complement M/A .

The Schur complement is a basic tool in many areas of matrix analysis and is a rich source of matrix inequalities. A fundamental result based on the Schur complement is widely found in convex optimization. Thanks to a fundamental property of the Schur complement which is going to be shown next, it is possible to convert a non-linear convex problem written in a particular form into an LMI problem. To achieve such result some linear algebra results must be introduced. Appendix A reports some useful information to undergo the next chapter.

4.4 Inertia of Hermitian matrices and Sylvester's law of inertia

This section is devoted to Sylvester's theorem (also known as Sylvester's law of inertia); the theory which is going to be shown has been selected from [23, pages 407, 408], [34, pages 27, 28], [21, pages 221-223] and [27, pages 568, 569].

Given an Hermitian matrix A (i.e. $A^* = A$), the inertia is a triple π, ν, ζ which respectively express the number of positive, negative and zero eigenvalues of matrix A counting algebraic multiplicities.

$$\text{In}(A) = (\pi, \nu, \zeta)$$

Note that the greek letter π (pi) is equivalent to the latin letter p which stands for *positive*; in the same spirit the greek letter ν (nu) is equivalent to the latin letter n which stands for *negative* and, finally, the greek letter ζ (zeta) is equivalent to the latin letter z which stands for *zero*.

In 1852 the English mathematician James Joseph Sylvester⁵ discovered that congruent matrices have the same inertia.

Theorem 8 (Sylvester's law of inertia) *Let A and B be two $n \times n$ Hermitian matrices then A and B are congruent if and only if they have the same inertia.*

Proof Since A is Hermitian there exist a unitary matrix P such that $A = P^{-1}\Lambda_A P$, where

⁵See [31] for his biography.

$$A \cong \hat{A} = \begin{bmatrix} I_\pi & & \\ & -I_\nu & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_\zeta \end{bmatrix}.$$

Proceeding in an analogous way, if $\text{In}(B) = (\Pi, \Theta, \Omega)$ then

$$B \cong \hat{B} = \begin{bmatrix} I_\Pi & & \\ & -I_\Theta & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_\Omega \end{bmatrix}.$$

If $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$ then $\hat{A} = \hat{B}$ and

$$A \cong \hat{A} = \hat{B} \cong B;$$

hence $A \cong B$. This means that, if $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$ then $A \cong B$. The second part of the proof consist in showing the contrary, i.e. if $A \cong B$ then $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$.

Since $A \cong \hat{A}$ and $B \cong \hat{B}$ then $\hat{A} \cong A \cong B \cong \hat{B}$ and, due to transitivity of *congruence, it follows that

$$\hat{A} \cong \hat{B}, \quad \text{i.e.}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_\pi & & \\ & -I_\nu & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_\zeta \end{bmatrix} \cong \begin{bmatrix} I_\Pi & & \\ & -I_\Theta & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_\Omega \end{bmatrix}.$$

Theorem 14 proves that congruent matrices have the same rank. Since $\hat{A} \cong A \cong B \cong \hat{B}$ then $\text{rank}\hat{A} = \text{rank}\hat{B}$ but

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rank}\hat{A} &= \pi + \nu \\ \text{rank}\hat{B} &= \Theta + \Omega; \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\text{rank}\hat{A} = \text{rank}\hat{B}$ implies

$$\zeta = \Omega;$$

and, particularly

$$\pi + \nu = \Pi + \Theta. \quad (4.4)$$

At this point it is enough to show that $\pi = \Pi$ to complete the proof. In fact we have just got that $\zeta = \Omega$ and if $\pi = \Pi$ then equation (4.4) also gives $\nu = \Theta$ and, putting all together; that means that $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$.

To show that $\pi = \Pi$ let's assume to the contrary that, for instance, $\pi > \Pi$ and, since $\hat{B} \cong \hat{A}^7$ then there must exist some nonsingular matrix S such that

$$\hat{B} = S^* \hat{A} S;$$

where S is partitioned conformally to \hat{A} and \hat{B} in the following manner:

$$S = [X_{n \times \Pi} \mid Y_{n \times (n-\Pi)}].$$

Observe that

$$S^* \hat{A} S = \begin{bmatrix} X_{\Pi \times n}^* \\ Y_{(n-\Pi) \times n}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_\pi & & \\ & -I_\nu & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_\zeta \end{bmatrix} [X_{n \times \Pi} \mid Y_{n \times (n-\Pi)}]$$

shows that S is partitioned correctly. Consider now the two following sets

$$\mathcal{M} = R(Y) = \text{rowsp}(Y) \subseteq \mathbb{F}^n \quad \text{and}$$

$$\mathcal{N} = \text{span}\{\mathbf{e}_1, \dots, \mathbf{e}_\pi\} \subseteq \mathbb{F}^n.$$

Theorem 13 affirms that

$$\dim(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) = \dim \mathcal{M} + \dim \mathcal{N} - \dim(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N});$$

then

$$\dim(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) = \dim \mathcal{M} + \dim \mathcal{N} - \dim(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}).$$

$\dim \mathcal{M} = \dim \mathcal{R}(Y) = \dim \text{rowsp}(Y)$ is the number of columns of matrix Y that is $n - \Pi$; furthermore $\dim \mathcal{N} = \dim \text{span}\{\mathbf{e}_1, \dots, \mathbf{e}_\pi\} = \pi$ then

$$\dim(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) = n - \Pi + \pi - \dim(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) = n + \pi - \Pi - \dim(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N});$$

But $\pi > \Pi$ hence $\pi - \Pi > 0$ and $\dim(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) > 0$. Consequently there exists a nonzero $n \times 1$ vector $x \in \mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$.

For such a vector $x \in \mathcal{M}$ implies that there exist a vector y such that

$$x = Yy \tag{4.5}$$

Equation 4.5 can also be thought as multiplying from the right matrix S (which contains submatrix Y) with a column vector with zeros on its upper part and matrix Y on its lower part, i.e.

$$x = Yy = S \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = [X_{n \times \Pi} \mid Y_{n \times (n-\Pi)}] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_\Pi \\ y_{(n-\Pi) \times 1} \end{bmatrix};$$

⁷Actually it is $\hat{A} \cong \hat{B}$ but theorem 15 ensures that congruency is an equivalence relation and, therefore, is also symmetric; thus $\hat{A} \cong \hat{B}$ implies $\hat{B} \cong \hat{A}$ and vice versa.

where in the last part of the equality subscripts relative to the dimensions have been added to show conform partitioning of submatrices and subvectors. Computing now $x^* \hat{A} x$ we have

$$x^* \hat{A} x = \left\{ S \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix} \right\}^* \hat{A} \left\{ S \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix} \right\} = [\mathbf{0}^* \mid y^*] S^* \hat{A} S \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = [\mathbf{0}^* \mid y^*] \hat{B} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix}$$

Where it has been exploited the fact that $\hat{B} = S^* \hat{A} S$; now

$$\begin{aligned} x^* \hat{A} x &= [\mathbf{0}^* \mid y^*] \hat{B} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ y \end{bmatrix} = [\mathbf{0}_{1 \times \Pi} \mid y_{1 \times (n-\Pi)}] \begin{bmatrix} I_{\Pi} & & \\ & -I_{\Theta} & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_{\Omega} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\Pi \times 1} \\ y_{(n-\Pi) \times 1} \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= y_{1 \times (n-\Pi)} \begin{bmatrix} -I_{\Theta} & \\ & \mathbf{0}_{\Omega} \end{bmatrix} y_{(n-\Pi) \times 1} = -y_{1 \times \Theta} I y_{\Theta \times 1} = -y_{1 \times \Theta} \cdot y_{\Theta \times 1} = -\|y_{\Theta}\|^2 \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since, also, $x \in \mathcal{N}$ and its sizes are $n \times 1$ then, by construction, x will have the following form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_{\pi} \\ \mathbf{0}_{(n-\pi) \times 1} \end{bmatrix};$$

computing again $x^* \hat{A} x$ we have

$$x^* \hat{A} x = [x_1, \dots, x_{\pi}, \mathbf{0}_{1 \times (n-\pi)}] \begin{bmatrix} I_{\pi} & & \\ & -I_{\nu} & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_{\zeta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_{\pi} \\ \mathbf{0}_{(n-\pi) \times 1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.6)$$

Observe that $\pi + \nu + \zeta = n$ hence $n - \pi = \nu + \zeta$ and (4.6) is partitioned correctly; in fact it becomes

$$\begin{aligned} x^* \hat{A} x &= [x_1, \dots, x_{\pi}, \mathbf{0}_{1 \times (\nu+\zeta)}] \begin{bmatrix} I_{\pi} & & \\ & -I_{\nu} & \\ & & \mathbf{0}_{\zeta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_{\pi} \\ \mathbf{0}_{(\nu+\zeta) \times 1} \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= [x_1, \dots, x_{\pi}] I_{\pi} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_{\pi} \end{bmatrix} = x_{1 \times \pi} I_{\pi} x_{\pi \times 1} = x_{1 \times \pi} \cdot x_{\pi \times 1} = \|\mathbf{x}_{\pi}\|^2 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Therefore it can't be $\pi > \Pi$. A similar argument shows that it is also impossible to have $\pi < \Pi$ so it must be $\pi = \Pi$ hence $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$ and this concludes the proof.

♣

4.5 The Schur complement applied to positive semidefinite matrices

Sylvester's law of inertia theorem is the key to prove the next theorem which is the basis of LMI theory. In fact it permits to convert a nonlinear convex problem to an equivalent LMI problem.

Theorem 9 *Let M be a Hermitian matrix partitioned as*

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^* & C \end{bmatrix}$$

in which A is square and nonsingular. Then

1. $M \succ 0$ *iff* $A \succ 0$ and $M/A \succ 0$;
2. $M \succeq 0$ *iff* $A \succ 0$ and $M/A \succeq 0$.

Proof To show both part 1) and 2) of the theorem consider matrix G as follows:

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix}.$$

Such a matrix exists because by hypothesis A is nonsingular (i.e. A^{-1} exists). Furthermore G is nonsingular by construction; hence, computing G^*MG we get a congruent matrix to M which is

$$\begin{aligned} G^*MG &= \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix}^* \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^* & C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} I & \mathbf{0} \\ -B^*(A^{-1})^* & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^* & C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} I & \mathbf{0} \\ -B^*(A^*)^{-1} & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^* & C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ -B^*(A^*)^{-1}A + B^* & -B^*(A^*)^{-1}B + C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ -B^* + B^* & -B^*(A^*)^{-1}B + C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ \mathbf{0} & -B^*(A^*)^{-1}B + C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & -A^{-1}B \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{bmatrix} = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \begin{bmatrix} A & -AA^{-1}B + B \\ \mathbf{0} & -B^*(A^*)^{-1}B + C \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} A & -B + B \\ \mathbf{0} & C - B^*(A^*)^{-1}B \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} A & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & C - B^*(A^*)^{-1}B \end{bmatrix}. \tag{4.7}
\end{aligned}$$

Where we have used the property⁸ $(A^{-1})^* = (A^*)^{-1}$. Observe that, since M is Hermitian (i.e. $M^* = M$), then A which is the principal submatrix of M is also Hermitian. Therefore $A^* = A$ and (4.7) becomes

$$G^*MG = \begin{bmatrix} A & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & C - B^*(A)^{-1}B \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & M/A \end{bmatrix}.$$

This means that

$$M \cong \begin{bmatrix} A & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & M/A \end{bmatrix}. \tag{4.8}$$

Applying Sylvester's theorem to (4.8) we have

$$\text{In}(M) = \text{In}(A) + \text{In}(M/A). \tag{4.9}$$

Equality (4.9) leads to the end of the proof; in fact

1. If $M \succ 0$ then all its eigenvalues are positive and so must be the eigenvalues of A and M/A ; that is

$$A \succ 0 \quad \text{and} \quad M/A \succ 0.$$

Since congruence is symmetric (see theorem 15 for a proof) then $A \succ 0$ and $M/A \succ 0$ implies $M \succeq 0$;

2. To prove the second part of the theorem observe that A is nonsingular. This also means that $\det A \neq 0$. If A were positive *semidefinite* there could be a zero eigenvalue that would set $\det A$ to zero. Hence A must be positive *definite* and so; in the same spirit of the previous point we can affirm that

$$M \succeq 0 \quad \text{iif} \quad A \succ 0 \quad \text{and} \quad M/A \succeq 0.$$

⁸In some texts, in fact, such commutative property is condensed into notation A^{-*} .

4.6 The Schur complement applied to the truss design problem

So far we have introduced the truss design problem as choosing proper volume bars (or section bars) such that compliance of the whole structure is minimized. This problem has been formalized in optimization problem 8 which, using (4.2), can be stated as

Optimization Problem 9

$$\begin{aligned} \min_t \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & \gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F \geq 0 \\ & \text{and various constraints.} \end{aligned}$$

Other constraints involve the volume of the structure. In fact the total allowed volume of the truss and the single bar volume is imposed by the features of the design. Formally this means

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^m t_i &\leq V_{\max} \\ t_{\min} &\leq t_i \leq t_{\max}. \end{aligned}$$

Usually t_{\min} is zero. By plugging these new constraints into optimization problem 9 then it becomes

Optimization Problem 10

$$\begin{aligned} \min_t \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & \gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F \geq 0 \\ & \sum_{i=1}^m t_i \leq V_{\max} \\ & t_{\min} \leq t_i \leq t_{\max}. \end{aligned}$$

Optimization problem 10 can already be a good point of reference to software developing relative to truss design; but we want to convert it into a better form. Suppose, for instance, that loads F are uncertain. As it will be shown in later chapters, uncertainty is represented by a new vector of variables δ which affect and complicate the algorithm. That is F will be composed by a nominal vector F_c and by a new vector containing uncertainty $F(\delta)$.

Clearly the expression $\gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F$ is not linear with respect to the new variables δ therefore it is harder to solve.

But viewing $\gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F$ as a Schur complement, we can convert optimization problem 10 into an LMI problem which is easier to solve. Hermitian matrices are simply symmetric matrices if their entries are real. This is the case of matrices involved in truss design. Therefore for a symmetric matrix $M = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B^T & C \end{pmatrix}$ its Schur complement relative to submatrix A is $M/A = C - B^T A^{-1} B$. Let's now compare M/A with the first constraint of optimization problem 10 by superimposing the two expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} M/A &= C - B^T A^{-1} B \\ &\gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F. \end{aligned}$$

It is very evident that γ plays the role of C ; B plays the role of F and $K(t)$ plays the role of A . With this comparison we can denote expression $\gamma - F^T K(t)^{-1} F$ as $M/K(t)$ and optimization problem 10 becomes

Optimization Problem 11

$$\begin{aligned} \min_t \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & M/K(t) \geq 0 \\ & \sum_{i=1}^m t_i \leq V_{\max} \\ & t_{\min} \leq t_i \leq t_{\max}. \end{aligned}$$

But applying theorem 9 to $M/K(t) \geq 0$ then we get a new equivalent optimization problem which is the one it has been taken as reference in writing the software for truss design algorithms.

Optimization Problem 12

$$\begin{aligned} \min_t \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & \begin{bmatrix} K(t) & F \\ F^T & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \\ & \sum_{i=1}^m t_i \leq V_{\max} \\ & t_{\min} \leq t_i \leq t_{\max}. \end{aligned}$$

4.7 The algorithm

We are now ready to show the MATLAB code relative to the convex optimization problem 12. Once that the user has specified the geometry of the lattice in matrix terms (together with the fixed nodes), the loads, the Young's moduli, then the algorithms will produce graphical results together with the optimized compliance and the rods volumes. At the end of the chapter three models will be shown. The first model is an example for a (rail)road bridge; the second example shows a crane model and finally the third example shows a sign support (such as a traffic light).

4.8 The MATLAB code and graphical results

In these sections we would like to show the MATLAB code edited for the truss design algorithm together with graphical results both before and after simulation about bridges, cranes and hanging signs.

4.8.1 bridgeSDP1.m

```
%*****  
% TRUSS TOPOLOGY  
%*****  
clear all  
close all  
  
Tx = 3;  
Ty = 2;  
  
TRUSS = zeros(Ty, Tx);  
TRUSS(Ty, 1) = -1;  
TRUSS(Ty, Tx) = -1;  
TRUSS  
TRUSS = TRUSS(end:-1:1, :);  
  
%*****  
% VECTOR "X"  
%*****  
  
% mappa che conta TUTTI i nodi progressivamente dal basso all'alto e da  
% sinistra a destra  
MAP1 = zeros(Ty, Tx);  
  
% mappa che conta progressivamente i soli nodi liberi dal basso all'alto e  
% da sinistra a destra
```

```

MAP2 = zeros(Ty, Tx);

% contatore di TUTTI i nodi per realizzare MAP1
num_nodes = 0;

% contatore per i soli nodi liberi per realizzare MAP2
free_nodes = 0;

% X è una matrice con le seguenti caratteristiche: la riga i di X si
% riferisce al nodo i e contiene le sue coordinate
X = [];

% FIXED è un vettore contenente i nodi fissi
FIXED = [];

% FREE è un vettore contenente i nodi liberi
FREE = [];

for ii = 1:1:Tx
    for jj = 1:1:Ty
        switch TRUSS(jj, ii)
            case 0 % nel caso di un nodo libero...
                % si aggiunge un nuovo nodo in MAP1
                num_nodes = num_nodes + 1;
                X = [X [ii; jj]];
                MAP1(jj, ii) = num_nodes;
                % si aggiunge un nuovo nodo in MAP2
                free_nodes = free_nodes + 1;
                MAP2(jj, ii) = free_nodes;
                % e si aggiorna il vettore FREE
                FREE = [FREE, num_nodes];
            case -1 % nel caso di un nodo fisso...
                % si aggiunge un nuovo nodo in MAP1
                num_nodes = num_nodes + 1;
                X = [X [ii; jj]];
                MAP1(jj, ii) = num_nodes;
                % si aggiorna il vettore FIXED
                FIXED = [FIXED, num_nodes];
                % NON si aggiunge un nodo libero
                % e si pone -1 in MAP2
                MAP2(jj, ii) = -1;
            otherwise % nel caso di un nodo proibito
                ; % non si fa niente
        end
    end
end

```

```

        end
    end
    MAP1 = MAP1(end:-1:1, :)
    MAP2 = MAP2(end:-1:1, :)

% Il numero di nodi è num_nodes
num_nodes

%*****
% VECTOR "L"
%*****

D = [ 1  1  2  1  3  2  3  1  3  2  3  1  2  1  1  0;
      -3 -2 -3 -1 -2 -1 -1 0  1  1  2  1  3  2  3  1 ];
dim = length(D);
L = [];
for n = 1:1:num_nodes
    % sto considerando il nodo ii di coordinate P
    P = X(:, n);

    % si tracciano tutte le barre possibili dal nodo P
    LINKED = [];
    for k = 1:1:dim
        % si calcolano le coordinate del nodo di destinazione
        DEST = P + D(:, k);

        % si controlla che il nodo di destinazione sia dentro il grigliato
        if DEST(1) >= 1 & DEST(1) <= Tx
            if DEST(2) >= 1 & DEST(2) <= Ty
                % si controlla che il nodo di destinazione non sia un nodo
                % proibito
                if TRUSS(DEST(2), DEST(1)) ~= 1
                    % si controlla che il nodo attuale e quello di destinazione
                    % non siano entrambi fissi
                    if TRUSS(P(2), P(1)) + TRUSS(DEST(2), DEST(1)) ~= -2
                        % in tutti gli altri casi si traccia una nuova barra.
                        % Si cerca in X il numero del nuovo nodo con la funzione
                        % find_node
                        new_node = find_node(DEST, X);
                        % si mette il nuovo nodo collegato con P nel vettore
                        % LINKED
                        LINKED = [LINKED new_node];
                    end
                end
            end
        end
    end
end
end

```

```

        end
    end
end

% si ordina il vettore LINKED con la funzione SORT
LINKED = sort(LINKED);

% si aggiorna il vettore L
for t = 1:1:length(LINKED)
    L = [L [n; LINKED(t)]];
end
end

% Il numero di barre è la lunghezza di L
numBars = length(L)

%*****
% VECTOR "LENGTHS"
%*****
% Il vettore LENGTHS contiene le lunghezze delle sbarre che compongono
% l'intera travatura. In particolare la posizione "i" si riferisce alla
% barra numero "i" e contiene la sua lunghezza.

% Poiché ci sono "numBars" barre, questa sarà la dimensione di LENGTHS
LENGTHS = zeros(1, numBars);

% Si esplora il vettore L
for n = 1:1:numBars
    % per ogni posizione di L ci sono i nodi estremi che chiamo
    % nodeA e nodeB
    nodeA = L(1, n);
    nodeB = L(2, n);
    % si calcola la loro distanza
    dist = norm(X(:, nodeA) - X(:, nodeB));
    % si aggiorna il vettore LENGTHS
    LENGTHS(n) = dist;
end

%*****
% VECTOR "F" (USER CONSTRUCTION)
%*****

F = zeros(2*freeNodes, 1);

```

```

%load = input('Enter the vertical load for each node of the bridge ');
load = -1e3;

% Vettore contenente i nodi dove si applicano le forze
LOADS = MAP2(end, 2:1:(end - 1));

dim = length(LOADS);
for n = 1:1:dim
    F(2*LOADS(n)) = load;
end

%*****
%  MATRIX "A"
%*****

A = [];

for n = 1:1:free_nodes
    % nodeA è il nodo attuale (libero) considerato
    nodeA = FREE(n);
    LINE_X = [];
    LINE_Y = [];
    % ora bisogna scorrere tutte le barre (quindi il vettore L)
    % e, se non è nel nodo di partenza, bisogna collocare degli
    % zeri nelle linee LINEX e LINEY della matrice A.
    for t = 1:1:num_bars
        if L(1, t) ~= nodeA & L(2, t) ~= nodeA
            LINE_X(t) = 0;
            LINE_Y(t) = 0;
        else
            % altrimenti si è trovata una barra che collega il
            % nodo libero attuale con un altro nodo che
            % chiamo nodeB. In particolare nodeB è

            if L(1, t) == nodeA
                nodeB = L(2, t);
            else
                nodeB = L(1, t);
            end

            % servono le coordinate P_A e P_B di nodeA e nodeB;
            % si ottengono dalla matrice X:
            P_A = X(:, nodeA);
            P_B = X(:, nodeB);
        end
    end
end

```

```

        % si calcola l'angolo tra i due punti
        DIFF = P_B - P_A;
        theta = atan2(DIFF(1), DIFF(2));
        % si riempono LINE_X (componenti orizzontali) e
        % LINE_Y (componenti verticali)
        LINE_X(t) = sin(theta);
        LINE_Y(t) = cos(theta);
    end
end
A = [A; LINE_X; LINE_Y];
end

%*****
%  OPTIMIZATION
%*****

% E is a vector containing the Young's moduli of every bar
E = 200e5*ones(1, num_bars)';

dummy = ones(1, num_bars);
% dummy variable to draw equal thickness bars
figure
makegraph(X, L, FIXED, num_bars, dummy)
title('INITIAL TRUSS TOPOLOGY')

V_max = 1e5;

optimization_SDP;

figure
makegraph(X, L, FIXED, num_bars, t)
title('TRUSS TOPOLOGY AFTER OPTIMIZATION')

```

4.8.2 Function find_node.m

```

function new_node = find_node(DEST, X)
position = 0;
found = 0;
while found == 0
    position = position + 1;
    if X(:, position) == DEST
        found = 1;
    end
end
end

```

```
new_node = position;
```

4.8.3 optimization_SDP.m

```
disp('Solver SDP')
t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);             % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
M = [K F; F' gamma];

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max) + set(M >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)
```

4.8.4 makegraph.m

```
function makegraph(X, L, FIXED, num_bars, x)
tol = 1e2;
% tollerance or minimum cross sectional area to draw a bar
%plot(X(1, :), X(2, :),'d')
if sum(x) == length(x)
    tol = 0;
    initial = 1;
else
    initial = 0;
end

hold on
for n = 1:1:num_bars
    if x(n) >= tol
        if initial ==1
            width = 0.7;
        else
            width = 5*abs(x(n))/max(x);
        end
    end
end
```

```

        end
        line([X(1, L(1, n)), X(1, L(2, n))], ...
            [X(2, L(1, n)), X(2, L(2, n))], 'LineWidth', width)
    end
end
for n = 1:1:length(FIXED)
    P = X(:, FIXED(n));
    Px = P(1);
    Py = P(2);
    plot(Px, Py, 'p')
end
xmin = min(X(1, :));
xmax = max(X(1, :));
ymin = min(X(2, :));
ymax = max(X(2, :));
axis([xmin-1 xmax+1 ymin-1 ymax+1])

```


Figure 4.1: A truss bridge.

Figure 4.2: A truss crane.

Figure 4.3: A truss hanging sign.

Figure 4.4: The initial lattice for a bigger truss bridge.

Figure 4.5: A bigger truss bridge.

Figure 4.6: A bigger crane.

Chapter 5

Convex optimization algorithms with uncertain parameters

In this chapter we deal with uncertain data such as uncertainty on the loads and on the Young's moduli and we will show more complex algorithms than those exposed in the previous chapter. These are used to solve the same problem (i.e. compliance minimization) but this time data is affected by uncertainty.

5.1 The convex hull

Figure 5.1a depicts a set C made up of eight points x_1, x_2, \dots, x_8 .

Starting from these points we can build up a so called *convex combination* which consists of new points of the form

$$\theta_1 x_1 + \theta_2 x_2 + \dots + \theta_8 x_8 \quad (5.1)$$

obtained by choosing coefficients $\theta_i \geq 0$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$ and such that

$$\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \dots + \theta_8 = 1.$$

Every time a new point is obtained through equation (5.1) by proper choice of coefficients θ_i ; it can be thought as a mixture of weighted average of the original points, with θ_i being the fraction of x_i in the mixture.

The *convex hull* of C is defined as the set of all convex combinations of points in C .

$$\mathbf{conv} C = \{\theta_1 x_1 + \theta_2 x_2 + \dots + \theta_8 x_8 \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, 8, \theta_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \theta_1 + \theta_2 + \dots + \theta_8 = 1.\} \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.1: a) C is a set of eight points. b) $\mathbf{conv} C$

The convex hull for set C of figure 5.1a is depicted in figure 5.1b. Note that the convex hull is *the smallest convex set which contains C* and of course, as the name suggests, is always convex. Such definition, of course, holds for every set C . In case, for instance, of k points, definition (5.2) becomes

$$\mathbf{conv} C = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i x_i \mid \theta_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i = 1. \right\} \quad (5.3)$$

The definition of convex hull also holds in the case of an infinity of points x_k ; in such case definition (5.4) becomes

$$\mathbf{conv} C = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \theta_i x_i \mid \theta_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \theta_i = 1, \right\} \quad (5.4)$$

provided the first series converges¹. This is the case, for instance, of figure 5.2. In figure 5.2a a non convex set C is shown. Such a set is definitely non convex because, as shown in figure 5.2b there are at least two points in C such that their segment does not completely lies on C . The convex hull $\mathbf{conv} C$ is depicted in figure 5.2c.

The concept of convex hull is useful to deal in problems regarding polytopic uncertainty.

¹By construction the second series does converge.

Figure 5.2: a) set C b) C isn't a convex set c) $\text{conv } C$.

5.2 Polytopic uncertainty

For the case of polytopic uncertainty it is shown next that algorithm 12 can be repeated just at every vertex of a convex hull rather than at any point of it. More formally the new algorithm is

Convex Optimization Problem 6

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{t, \gamma} \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & l^T t \leq V_{\max} \\ & \begin{bmatrix} K(t, \theta_i) & F_i \\ F_i^T & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, v. \end{aligned}$$

In [13] it is proved that the following convex optimization problem with LMI constraints on x and on the uncertainty δ

Convex Optimization Problem 7

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f(x) \quad \text{subject to} \\ & f(x) \text{ is convex and} \\ & F(x, \delta) \triangleq F_0(\delta) + \sum_{i=1}^m F_i(\delta) \succeq 0 \quad \forall \delta \in \Delta \end{aligned}$$

can be converted in a simpler problem where uncertainty is evaluated at the vertices of its associated convex hull $\mathbf{conv} \Delta$ only; i.e. $F(x, \delta_i)$. Such a powerful result permits to convert a semi-infinite constraint $F(x, \delta) \succeq 0$ into a *finite number* of LMI constraints. This is formalized in the next theorem taken from [13].

Theorem 10 *Let $F(x, \delta) \succeq 0$ be an LMI in $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ written as $F(x, \delta) \triangleq F_0(\delta) + \sum_{i=1}^m F_i(\delta)$ with $F_i(\delta) = F_i^T(\delta)$ are affine functions of δ . Let $\delta \in \Delta$, where Δ is a polytope of vertices $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_v$; then*

$$F(x, \delta) \succeq 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad F(x, \delta_i) \succeq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, v.$$

Proof The implication from the left to the right is obvious; hence we prove the reverse implication. Since $\delta \in \mathbf{conv} \Delta$ then by convex hull definition 5.1 there exist positive $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_v$ such that

$$\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \dots + \theta_v = \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i = 1$$

and

$$\delta = \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i \delta_i;$$

where δ_i are the vertexes of $\mathbf{conv} \Delta$. Since $F(x, \delta)$ is affine in δ we can express it as

$$F(x, \delta) = F(x, 0) + \tilde{F}(x, \delta);$$

with $\tilde{F}(x, \delta)$ linear in δ . Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned} F(x, \delta) &= F(x, 0) + \tilde{F}(x, \delta) = \\ &= F(x, 0) + \left(\tilde{F}(x, \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i \delta_i) \right); \end{aligned}$$

but $\tilde{F}(x, \delta)$ is linear in δ hence

$$\begin{aligned} F(x, \delta) &= F(x, 0) + \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i \tilde{F}(x, \delta_i) = \\ &= 1 \cdot F(x, 0) + \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i \tilde{F}(x, \delta_i) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i F(x, 0) + \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i \tilde{F}(x, \delta_i) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i (F(x, 0) + \tilde{F}(x, \delta_i)) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^v \theta_i F(x, \delta_i) \succeq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Some examples together with their MATLAB code are next shown.

5.2.1 A bridge with nominal components

Consider a truss bridge with three horizontal nodes and two vertical nodes. Using `bridgeSDP1.m` the following results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 33335 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33318 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33335 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.0255N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{ cm}^3.$$

Figure 5.3: All connections before optimization.

5.2.2 The same bridge with one uncertain load component

Solver `optimization_one_load1.m` is used in place of `optimization_SDP` (which is only used for nominal data). `optimization_one_load1.m` is reported next.

Figure 5.4: Truss bridge.

```

disp('Solver SDP_one_load1')
perc = 0.1/100;
F1 = F;
F1(2*LOADS) = load - load*perc;
F2 = F;
F2(2*LOADS) = load - load*perc;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);      % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);      % upper bound for the compliance of the truss

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max);

M1 = [K F1; F1' gamma];
M2 = [K F2; F2' gamma];

CC = CC + set(M1 >= 0) + set(M2 >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

```

```

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

The following results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 33321 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33351 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33321 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.0255\text{N} \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{cm}^3.$$

5.2.3 The same bridge with the load having both of its components uncertain.

In this example the load is supposed to have both of its components (i.e F_x and F_y) uncertain. Solver `optimization_one_load2` has been used which code is here reported.

```

disp('Solver SDP_one_load2')
perc = 0.1/100;
F1 = F;
F1(2*LOADS - 1) = - load*perc;
F1(2*LOADS) = load - load*perc;
F2 = F;
F2(2*LOADS - 1) = - load*perc;
F2(2*LOADS) = load + load*perc;
F3 = F;
F3(2*LOADS - 1) = + load*perc;

```


Figure 5.5: Truss bridge with one uncertain load component.

```

F3(2*LOADS) = load - load*perc;
F4 = F;
F4(2*LOADS - 1) = + load*perc;
F4(2*LOADS) = load + load*perc;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);             % upper bound for the compliance of the truss

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max);

M1 = [K F1; F1' gamma];
M2 = [K F2; F2' gamma];
M3 = [K F3; F3' gamma];
M4 = [K F4; F4' gamma];

CC = CC + set(M1 >= 0) + set(M2 >= 0) + set(M3 >= 0) + set(M4 >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

```

```

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

The following results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 33310 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33340 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33310 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.0255N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{ cm}^3.$$

Figure 5.6: Truss bridge with the load having both of its components uncertain.

5.2.4 A bridge with two nominal loads.

Using solver `optimization_SDP.m` the following results have been obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 28561 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14293 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14291 \\ 0 \\ 14293 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 28561 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.1225N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{cm}^3$$

5.2.5 A bridge with two uncertain loads.

Solver `optimization_three_loads` has been used which code is here reported.

```

disp('Solver SDP_two_loads')
perc = 0.1/100;
F1 = F;
F1(2*LOADS(1)) = load - load*perc;
F1(2*LOADS(2)) = load - load*perc;
F2 = F;
F2(2*LOADS(1)) = load - load*perc;
F2(2*LOADS(2)) = load + load*perc;
F3 = F;
F3(2*LOADS(1)) = load + load*perc;
F3(2*LOADS(2)) = load - load*perc;
F4 = F;
F4(2*LOADS(1)) = load + load*perc;
F4(2*LOADS(2)) = load + load*perc;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);           % upper bound for the compliance of the truss

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max);

M1 = [K F1; F1' gamma];
M2 = [K F2; F2' gamma];
M3 = [K F3; F3' gamma];
M4 = [K F4; F4' gamma];

CC = CC + set(M1 >= 0) + set(M2 >= 0) + set(M3 >= 0) + set(M4 >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')

```

```

U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

The following results have been obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 28556 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14291 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14294 \\ 0 \\ 14291 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 28556 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.1225N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{cm}^3$$

Figure 5.7: All connections before optimization.

Figure 5.8: A truss bridge with two loads.

5.2.6 A bridge with three nominal loads.

Using solver `optimization_SDP.m` the following results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 15798 \\ 14076 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 7145 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1511 \\ 8653 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 5633 \\ 0 \\ 1511 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 8653 \\ 14076 \\ 7145 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 15798 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.49N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{cm}^3.$$

5.2.7 A bridge with three uncertain loads.

Solver `optimization_three_loads` has been used which code is here reported.

Figure 5.9: A truss bridge with two uncertain loads.

```

disp('Solver SDP_three_loads')
perc = 0.1/100;

for n = 1:8
    f(:, :) = F;
end

f(LOADS(1), 1:4) = F(LOADS(1))*(1 - perc);
f(LOADS(1), 5:8) = F(LOADS(1))*(1 + perc);

f(LOADS(2), 1:2) = F(LOADS(2))*(1 - perc);
f(LOADS(2), 3:4) = F(LOADS(2))*(1 + perc);
f(LOADS(2), 5:6) = F(LOADS(2))*(1 - perc);
f(LOADS(2), 7:8) = F(LOADS(2))*(1 + perc);

for n = 1:8
    f(LOADS(3), n) = F(LOADS(3))*(1 + (-1)^n*perc);
end

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

```

```

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);    % upper bound for the compliance of the truss

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max);

for n = 1:8
    M = [K f(:, n); f(:, n)' gamma];
    CC = CC + set(M >= 0);
end

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

The following results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 16043 \\ 13440 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 7142 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1768 \\ 8912 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 5377 \\ 0 \\ 1769 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 8919 \\ 13422 \\ 7149 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 16057 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.49N \times \text{cm}.$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{ cm}^3.$$

5.3 Norm-bounded uncertainty on loadings.

This section regards all those kinds of trusses where Young's moduli are exactly known and the external forces F belong to an ellipsoid \mathcal{E} of center F_c and shape matrix W , i.e.

$$\mathcal{E} = \{F = F_c + Wz, \quad \text{with} \quad \|z\| \leq 1\}. \quad (5.5)$$

Figure 5.10: Truss bridge with three uncertain loads.

The algorithm is

Convex Optimization Problem 8

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{t, \gamma, \tau} \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & l^T t \leq V_{\max} \\ & \begin{bmatrix} K(t, \theta) - \tau W W^T & F_c & \mathbf{0} \\ F_c^T & \gamma & 1 \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 & \tau \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0. \end{aligned}$$

5.3.1 The ellipse

The ellipse² is the locus of points $P(x, y)$ in a plane such that the sum of the distances to two fixed points $F(c, 0)$ and $F'(-c, 0)$ called *foci* are constant. Let $2a$ be the constant sum of distances; hence, from figure 5.11 we have:

$$\overline{PF'} + \overline{PF} = 2a.$$

Therefore:

$$\sqrt{(x+c)^2 + y^2} + \sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} = 2a$$

²The theory which is going to be shown has been taken from [39, pages 193-195].

Figure 5.11: The ellipse.

$$\begin{aligned}
\sqrt{(x+c)^2 + y^2} &= 2a - \sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} \\
(x+c)^2 + y^2 &= 4a^2 - 4a\sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} + (x-c)^2 + y^2 \\
4a\sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} &= 4a^2 + (x-c)^2 + y^2 - (x+c)^2 - y^2 \\
4a\sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} &= 4a^2 + x^2 - 2cx + c^2 - x^2 - 2cx - c^2 \\
4a\sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} &= 4a^2 - 4cx \\
a\sqrt{(x-c)^2 + y^2} &= a^2 - cx \\
a\sqrt{x^2 - 2cx + c^2 + y^2} &= a^2 - cx \\
a^2(x^2 - 2cx + c^2 + y^2) &= a^4 - 2a^2cx + c^2x^2 \\
a^2x^2 - 2a^2cx + a^2c^2 + a^2y^2 &= a^4 - 2a^2cx + c^2x^2 \\
a^2x^2 + a^2c^2 + a^2y^2 &= a^4 + c^2x^2 \\
(a^2 - c^2)x^2 + a^2y^2 &= a^4 - a^2c^2 \\
(a^2 - c^2)x^2 + a^2y^2 &= a^2(a^2 - c^2). \tag{5.6}
\end{aligned}$$

Since every side of a triangle is less than the sum of the other two sides, then, considering triangle FPF'

$$F'F < PF' + PF$$

But $F'F = 2c$ and $PF' + PF = 2a$ hence

$$2c < 2a$$

or

$$c < a.$$

Since $c < a$ ($a > c$) then $a^2 - c^2$ in (5.6) is positive and a new term b is introduced as follows:

$$b^2 = a^2 - c^2. \quad (5.7)$$

Therefore equation (5.6) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} b^2x^2 + a^2y^2 &= a^2b^2 \\ \frac{b^2x^2 + a^2y^2}{a^2b^2} &= \frac{a^2b^2}{a^2b^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1 \quad (5.8)$$

Equation (5.8) is the *canonical* or *normal equation of the ellipse*. A figure of merit of the ellipse is the *eccentricity* e which is defined as the ratio

$$e = \frac{c}{a}.$$

5.3.2 Examples

One load bridge with both of its components uncertain

Consider, again, the example of the bridge with one load having both of its components uncertain. The nominal external forces vector is

$$F_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (F_{2,x}) \\ (F_{2,y}) \\ (F_{3,x}) \\ (F_{3,y}) \\ (F_{4,x}) \\ (F_{4,y}) \\ (F_{5,x}) \\ (F_{5,y}) \end{bmatrix} N. \quad (5.9)$$

Particularly $F_{3,x} = 0$ and $F_{3,y} = -1000$. Since the radius of the interval of uncertainty is assumed to be 0.01 times the nominal load (i.e. 1000N), then the radius is $0.01 \times 1000N = 10N$ and

$$\begin{aligned} -10N &\leq F_{3,x} \leq +10N \\ -1010N &\leq F_{3,y} \leq +1010N. \end{aligned}$$

This means that in order to get the shape matrix W , equation of the ellipse of center $(0, -1000)N$ and semiaxis both of $10 N$. This is an easy case because, since both semiaxis are equal, the ellipse becomes a circumference (i.e. its eccentricity $e = 0$). The desired circumference is the one of center $(0, -1000)N$ and radius $r = 10\sqrt{2}$, i.e.

$$x^2 + (y + 1000)^2 = 200.$$

The reason why we have chosen a radius $r = 10\sqrt{2}$ rather than 10 is illustrated in figure 5.14 where the associated circumference having the origin as center is depicted. The circumference, indeed, must enclose the square of

Figure 5.12: The associated circumference in the example.

side 10 hence its radius must be $10\sqrt{2}$. Now we must form the shape matrix W remembering that

$$F = F_c + Wz \quad \text{with} \quad \|z\| \leq 1$$

From equation (5.9) we can write the following:

$$F = F_c + Wz = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 10\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 10\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{3,x} \\ z_{3,y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Applying algorithm (9) to the example the same result is obtained in accordance to the nominal case.

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 33270 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33304 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 33270 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3,$$

where software optimization_W_one_load2 has been used. Its code is reported next.

```
disp('Solver SDP_W_one_load2')
perc = 0.1/100;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1, 1);           % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
tau = sdpvar(1, 1);

W = zeros(length(F));
W(3, 3) = perc*abs(load)*sqrt(2);
W(4, 4) = perc*abs(load)*sqrt(2);
```

```

M = [ K - tau*W*W', F, zeros(length(F), 1);
      F', gamma, 1;
      zeros(1, length(F)), 1, tau];

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max) + set(M >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

Two loads bridge having the same uncertainty ray

In the nominal case the nominal external forces vector is

$$F_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (F_{2,x}) \\ 0 & (F_{2,y}) \\ 0 & (F_{3,x}) \\ -1000 & (F_{3,y}) \\ 0 & (F_{4,x}) \\ 0 & (F_{4,y}) \\ 0 & (F_{5,x}) \\ -1000 & (F_{5,y}) \\ 0 & (F_{6,x}) \\ 0 & (F_{6,y}) \\ 0 & (F_{8,x}) \\ 0 & (F_{8,y}) \end{bmatrix} N. \quad (5.10)$$

Let's suppose that lodes on nodes three and five are uncertain with relative uncertainty of 0.01 (i.e. 1%); this means that

$$\begin{aligned} -10N &\leq F_{3,y} \leq +10N \\ -10N &\leq F_{5,y} \leq +10N. \end{aligned}$$

Then, proceeding as in the previous example, we get

$$F = F_c + Wz = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 10\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 10\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{3,y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{5,y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using solver `optimization_W_two_loads1.m` (reported next), we find the following results in accordance to the nominal case:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 28548 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14271 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14275 \\ 0 \\ 14271 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 28548 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

```
disp('Solver SDP_W_two_loads1')
perc = 0.1/100;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1, 1);           % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
```

```

tau = sdpvar(1, 1);

W = zeros(length(F));
W(4, 4) = perc*abs(load)*sqrt(2);
W(8, 8) = perc*abs(load)*sqrt(2);

M = [ K - tau*W*W', F, zeros(length(F), 1);
      F', gamma, 1;
      zeros(1, length(F)), 1, tau];

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max) + set(M >= 0);

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

Two loads bridge having different uncertainty rays

So far we have considered the case of equal uncertainty rays, i.e. the polytope is a cube. If the uncertainty rays are different then the polytope is a iper-parallelepiped which reduces to a rectangle in the plane. This is the case studied in this example. This means that, given a point $P(\alpha, \beta)$ in the plane where α and β are the two uncertainty rays; we wish to find the equation of the ellipse which contains the rectangle of vertexes $P(\alpha, \beta)$, the points $(-\alpha, \beta)$, $(-\alpha, -\beta)$, $(\alpha, -\beta)$ and such that the area of the ellipse is minimum. This is depicted in figure 5.13.

Consider a generic ellipse γ of equation

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$$

Implying $P(\alpha, \beta) \in \gamma$ we have

$$\frac{\alpha^2}{a^2} + \frac{\beta^2}{b^2} = 1.$$

The same equation would be obtained if we imposed all the other vertexes being on the ellipse. Hence we need one more equation to both determine semiaxis a and b to plug into matrix W . This equation comes from requiring the area of the ellipsis must be minimum. To find the area of the ellipse

Figure 5.13: An ellipse including the four points of the problem.

integration is required. To do so we just consider the upper part of the ellipse which can be expressed as a function³ and integrate it over interval $[-a, +a]$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} &= 1 \\ \frac{y^2}{b^2} &= 1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} \\ \frac{y}{b} &= \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}} \\ y &= \pm b \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

The area S of the ellipse is then

$$S = 2 \int_{-a}^{+a} b \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}} dx = 2b \int_{-a}^{+a} \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}} dx. \quad (5.11)$$

With substitution $x = a \sin t$ we get

³The ellipse itself, in fact, it is not a function.

$$\begin{aligned}x &= a \sin t \\dx &= a \cos t dt\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}x = -a &\implies -a = a \sin t \implies \sin t = -1 \implies t = -\frac{\pi}{2}; \\x = a &\implies a = a \sin t \implies \sin t = 1 \implies t = \frac{\pi}{2}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence integral (5.11) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}S &= 2b \int_{-a}^{+a} \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}} dx = 2b \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{(a \sin t)^2}{a^2}} a \cos t dt = \\&= 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{a^2 \sin^2 t}{a^2}} \cos t dt = 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 t} \cos t dt = \\&= 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{\cos^2 t} \cos t dt = 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos t \cos t dt = 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^2 t dt.\end{aligned}\tag{5.12}$$

To integrate $\cos^2 t$ consider the following equality:

$$\cos 2t = \cos^2 t - \sin^2 t = \cos^2 t - (1 - \cos^2 t) = \cos^2 t - 1 + \cos^2 t = 2 \cos^2 t - 1;$$

therefore

$$2 \cos^2 t = 1 + \cos 2t \implies \cos^2 t = \frac{1 + \cos 2t}{2}$$

and integral (5.12) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}S &= 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^2 t dt = 2ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{1 + \cos 2t}{2} dt = ab \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} (1 + \cos 2t) dt = \\&= ab \left[t + \frac{1}{2} \sin 2t \right]_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{+\frac{\pi}{2}} = ab \left[\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sin \left(2 \frac{\pi}{2} \right) - \left(-\frac{\pi}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \sin \left(-2 \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] = \\&= ab \left[\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sin(\pi) + \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sin(\pi) \right] = ab \left[\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2} \right] = \pi ab.\end{aligned}$$

So far we have got two items of information which are

$$\boxed{
\begin{array}{ll}
\frac{\alpha^2}{a^2} + \frac{\beta^2}{b^2} = 1 & P \in \gamma; \\
S = \pi ab & \text{area of the ellipse } \gamma.
\end{array}
} \tag{5.13}$$

The last information to exploit is that the area of the ellipse must be minimum. To do so one has to put together equations (5.13) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\alpha^2}{a^2} + \frac{\beta^2}{b^2} &= 1 \\
\frac{\beta^2}{b^2} &= 1 - \frac{\alpha^2}{a^2} \\
\frac{\beta}{b} &= \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{\alpha^2}{a^2}} \\
\frac{b}{\beta} &= \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\alpha^2}{a^2}}} \\
b &= \pm \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\alpha^2}{a^2}}} = \\
&= \pm \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{\frac{a^2 - \alpha^2}{a^2}}} = \\
&= \pm \frac{\beta}{\frac{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}{a}} = \\
&= \pm \frac{a\beta}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Since all the quantities are positive then we just take the positive square root:

$$b = + \frac{a\beta}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}. \tag{5.14}$$

But $S = \pi ab$ then

$$S = \pi a \frac{a\beta}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} = \frac{\pi a^2 \beta}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} = \pi \beta \frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}.$$

Since the area of the ellipse must be minimum then we have to find that particular value of a such that $\frac{\partial S}{\partial a} = 0$; then we have

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial a} = \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left(\pi \beta \frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} \right) = \pi \beta \left(\frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} \right) =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \pi\beta \frac{2a\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} - a^2 \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} 2a}{a^2 - \alpha^2} = \pi\beta \frac{2a\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} - \frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} a}{a^2 - \alpha^2} = \\
&= \pi\beta a \frac{2\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} - \frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}}{a^2 - \alpha^2} = \pi\beta a \frac{\frac{2(a^2 - \alpha^2) - a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}}{a^2 - \alpha^2} = \pi\beta a \frac{2(a^2 - \alpha^2) - a^2}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \\
&= \pi\beta a \frac{2a^2 - 2\alpha^2 - a^2}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \pi\beta a \frac{a^2 - 2\alpha^2}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \pi\beta \frac{a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then the values of a such that the area of the ellipse is minimum are those which satisfy the equation

$$a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2) = 0.$$

A first solution is $a = 0$ but this is a non admissible solution since $a = 0$ means an ellipse having a semi axis of length zero! The other solutions are

$$a^2 - 2\alpha^2 = 0 \implies a^2 = 2\alpha^2 \implies a = \pm\sqrt{2}\alpha.$$

Again we don't consider negative or null solutions since a is the length of a semi axis; therefore the solution which minimizes the area of the ellipse is

$$a = \sqrt{2}\alpha;$$

which (see equation (5.14)) corresponds the following value of b :

$$b = \frac{a\beta}{\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\alpha\beta}{\sqrt{2\alpha^2 - \alpha^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\alpha\beta}{\sqrt{\alpha^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\alpha\beta}{\alpha} = \sqrt{2}\beta.$$

To be sure that the solution is really a minimum point we must check that the second order derivative of S with respect to a must be negative when evaluated at the stationary point which, in this case is $a = \sqrt{2}\alpha$; i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial a^2} \Big|_{a=\sqrt{2}\alpha} > 0. \\
\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial a^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \frac{\partial S}{\partial a} = \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left(\pi\beta \frac{a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) = \pi\beta \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left(\frac{a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) = \\
&= \pi\beta \frac{(a^2 - 2\alpha^2 + a \cdot 2a)(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} - a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2) \cdot \frac{3}{2}(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}-1}}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta \frac{(a^2 - 2\alpha^2 + 2a^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} - \frac{3}{2}a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta \frac{(3a^2 - 2\alpha^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2)^{1+\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{3}{2}a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3} =
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \pi\beta \frac{(3a^2 - 2\alpha^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2)\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} - \frac{3}{2}a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2}}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} \frac{(3a^2 - 2\alpha^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2) - \frac{3}{2}a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta\sqrt{a^2 - \alpha^2} \frac{2(3a^2 - 2\alpha^2)(a^2 - \alpha^2) - 3a(a^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{2(a^2 - \alpha^2)^3}. \\
\left. \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial a^2} \right|_{a=\sqrt{2}\alpha} &= \pi\beta\sqrt{2\alpha^2 - \alpha^2} \frac{2(3 \cdot 2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha^2)(2\alpha^2 - \alpha^2) - 3\sqrt{2}\alpha(2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha^2)}{2(2\alpha^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta\sqrt{\alpha^2} \frac{2(6\alpha^2 - 2\alpha^2)\alpha^2 - 3\sqrt{2}\alpha \cdot 0}{2(2\alpha^2 - \alpha^2)^3} = \\
&= \pi\beta\alpha \frac{2 \cdot 4\alpha^2 \cdot \alpha^2}{2(\alpha^2)^3} = \pi\alpha\beta \frac{8\alpha^4}{2\alpha^6} = 4\pi \frac{\beta}{\alpha} > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence the solution $a = \sqrt{2}\alpha$ and $b = \sqrt{2}\beta$ is the one which minimizes the area of the ellipse. Note that, if $\alpha = \beta$ then we find again the result of the case equal uncertainty rays. In the previous cases we had $|F_c| = 1000N$ and relative uncertainty $0.01 = 1\%$. Therefore the uncertainty ray is $1000N \times 1\% = 1000N \times 0.01 = 10N$. In the next example we consider the case of a two loads bridge where such loads have different uncertainty rays. Particularly we study the case in which the first load has a relative uncertainty of 1% whilst the second load has a relative uncertainty of 3% . This means that the first load has an uncertainty load of $1000N \times 1\% = \frac{1000N}{100} = 10N = \alpha$ whilst the second load has an uncertainty load of $1000N \times 3\% = 1000N \times \frac{3}{100} = 30N = \beta$. So $a = \sqrt{2}\alpha = 10\sqrt{2}N$; $b = \sqrt{2}\beta = 30\sqrt{2}N$ and then we can build up matrix W .

$$F = F_c + Wz = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 10\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 30\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{3,y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{5,y} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using solver `optimization_W_two_loads2.m` (reported next), we find the following results in accordance to the nominal case:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 28504 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14259 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14257 \\ 0 \\ 14313 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 28576 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

```

disp('Solver SDP_W_two_loads2')
perc1 = 0.1/100;
perc2 = 0.3/100;

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));

K = A*invB*A';
gamma = sdpvar(1, 1);           % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
tau = sdpvar(1, 1);

W = zeros(length(F));
W(4, 4) = perc1*abs(load)*sqrt(2);
W(8, 8) = perc2*abs(load)*sqrt(2);

M = [ K - tau*W*W', F, zeros(length(F), 1);
      F', gamma, 1;
      zeros(1, length(F)), 1, tau];

CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max) + set(M >= 0);

```

```

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)

```

5.3.3 The Löwner-John ellipsoid

When the number of uncertain loads is bigger than two the previous formulas are no longer useful because they only cover the case of two uncertain loads. Anyway the problem is still the same but more generale: determine the minimum volume ellipsoid which covers the polytope describing uncertainty. Such an ellipsoid is known as *Löwner-John ellipsoid* which theory can be found, for instance, in [7, pages 410-414]. In (5.5) we have described an ellipsoid \mathcal{E} as the set of points F such that

$$\mathcal{E} = \{F \mid F = F_c + Wz, \quad \text{with} \quad \|z\| \leq 1\}. \quad (5.15)$$

Another common way to define an ellipsoid \mathcal{E} is the set of points F such that

$$\mathcal{E} = \{F \mid \|CF + d\| \leq 1\}. \quad (5.16)$$

Notation (5.15) is found, for instance, in [13] whilst notation (5.16) appears in [7, pages 410-414]. Before proceeding in showing the algorithm to determine Löwner-John ellipsoid we want to show that (5.15) and (5.16) are equivalent. In fact from

$$F = F_c + Wz$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
F - F_c &= Wz \\
Wz &= F - F_c \\
z &= W^{-1}(F - F_c) \\
z &= W^{-1}F - W^{-1}F_c.
\end{aligned}$$

But $\|z\| \leq 1$ implies

$$\|W^{-1}F - W^{-1}F_c\| \leq 1;$$

which compared to (5.16) gives

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \| W^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} F & -W^{-1}F_c \end{bmatrix} \| \leq 1 \\ \| \begin{bmatrix} C & F \\ & +d \end{bmatrix} \| \leq 1 \end{array} \right\} \implies \begin{cases} C = W^{-1} \\ d = W^{-1}F_c \end{cases}$$

Matrix W is diagonal and contains semiaxis of the ellipsoid therefore the volume depends on the determinant (i.e. the product of the components on the diagonal) of W . In our previous examples matrix W was sparse and singular because it also included all those nominal components not affected by uncertainty having, indeed, a null uncertainty ray therefore a zero entry in matrix W . In this section we consider a submatrix \tilde{W} of W by selecting only uncertain loads. After that matrix W can be easily formed. With this choice \tilde{W} is clearly nonsingular and the volume of the ellipsoid depends on $\det \tilde{W} = \det C^{-1}$ which must be minimized. If we name the diagonal entries of \tilde{W} as $\tilde{w}_1, \tilde{w}_2, \dots, \tilde{w}_\sigma$ then

$$\det C^{-1} = \det \tilde{W} = \tilde{w}_1 \times \tilde{w}_2 \times \dots \times \tilde{w}_\sigma = \prod_{i=1}^{\sigma} \tilde{w}_i,$$

which is not a convex function. That's why, actually the cost function is $\ln \det C^{-1}$ rather than $\det C^{-1}$ in fact

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \det C^{-1} &= \ln \det \tilde{W} = \ln \prod_{i=1}^{\sigma} \tilde{w}_i = \ln(\tilde{w}_1 \times \tilde{w}_2 \times \dots \times \tilde{w}_\sigma) = \\ &= \ln \tilde{w}_1 + \ln \tilde{w}_2 + \dots + \ln \tilde{w}_\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^{\sigma} \ln \tilde{w}_i \end{aligned}$$

which is a convex function. Let \mathcal{D} be the volume surrounded by the Löwner-John ellipsoid then the constraints are

1. $C^{-1} \succ 0$ or $C \succ 0$ in fact \tilde{W} (i.e. C^{-1}) is a diagonal matrix having the semiaxis on its diagonal which are obviously positive;
2. $\sup_{F \in \mathcal{D}} \|CF + d\| \leq 1$. This constraint means that the points on the edge of volume \mathcal{D} can't be greater than the ellipsoid itself; i.e. they are contained into the ellipsoid or, at most, they lie on it.

Therefore the problem of finding \tilde{W} is

Optimization Problem 13

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \ln \det C^{-1} \quad \text{subject to} \\ & C \succ 0 \\ & \sup_{F \in \mathcal{D}} \|CF + d\| \leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

If volume \mathcal{D} can be described by a finite set of vertexes $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_\sigma$ then problem 13 becomes

Optimization Problem 14

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \ln \det C^{-1} \quad \text{subject to} \\ & C \succ 0 \\ & \|CF_i + d\| \leq 1, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

In our case volume \mathcal{D} is a hyper-rectangle which vertexes lie on the ellipsoid therefore the inequalities of the second constraint become equalities:

Optimization Problem 15

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \ln \det C^{-1} \quad \text{subject to} \\ & C \succ 0 \\ & \|CF_i + d\| = 1, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

By squaring the second constraints we have

$$\|CF_i + d\|^2 = 1^2 = 1.$$

But

$$\begin{aligned} \|CF_i + d\|^2 &= (CF_i + d)^* \cdot (CF_i + d) = \\ &= (F_i^* C^* + d^*) \cdot (CF_i + d) = \\ &= F_i^* C^* CF_i + F_i^* C^* d + d^* CF_i + d^* d = \\ &= (CF_i)^* CF_i + (d^* CF_i)^* + d^* CF_i + d^* d = \\ &= \|CF_i\|^2 + (d^* CF_i)^* + d^* CF_i + \|d\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (5.17)$$

Note that $\|CF_i + d\|^2$ is a real number and so are $(d^* CF_i)^*$ and $d^* CF_i$. But, for any scalar c we have that $c^* = c^T = c$ hence $(d^* CF_i)^* = d^* CF_i$ and (5.17) becomes

$$\|CF_i + d\|^2 = \|CF_i\|^2 + 2d^* CF_i + \|d\|^2.$$

So problem 15 becomes

Optimization Problem 16

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \ln \det C^{-1} \quad \text{subject to} \\ & C \succ 0 \\ & \|CF_i\|^2 + 2d^* CF_i + \|d\|^2 = 1, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

5.4 Generic uncertainty on loadings and Young's moduli.

So far all the algorithms dealing with uncertainty have minimized the worst case. This class of algorithms is called *robust*. In this section we want to show an alternative philosophy to solve the uncertain problem. Instead of minimizing the worst case we seek for an approximate solution but with a given accuracy ϵ and a probability of violation β . This means that with a probability $1 - \beta$ the solution has the desired accuracy ϵ . Fixed these two number it is possible to determine the number N of samples $\delta^{(1)}, \delta^{(2)}, \dots, \delta^{(N)}$, involved in the problem. The set of such values is called *scenario* and we express the approximate solution as $\hat{x}_{WC}^{(N)}$.

More formally we can state the problem as follows: fix two real numbers ϵ and β both in $(0, 1)$ respectively the robustness level and the confidence parameter and let

$$N \geq N_{WC}(\epsilon, \beta) \triangleq \left\lceil \frac{2}{\epsilon} \ln \frac{1}{\beta} + 2(n+1) + \frac{2(n+1)}{\epsilon} \ln \frac{2}{\epsilon} \right\rceil$$

then, with probability no smaller than $1 - \beta$ we have that $\hat{x}_{WC}^{(N)}$ is ϵ -level robustly feasible. The algorithm becomes

Convex Optimization Problem 9

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{t, \gamma} \quad & \gamma \quad \text{subject to} \\ & l^T t \leq V_{\max} \\ & \begin{bmatrix} K(t, \theta^{(i)}) & F^{(i)} \\ (F^{(i)})^T & \gamma \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N. \end{aligned}$$

5.5 An example

Let's revisit again the example of the bridge with three uncertain loads. This time also the Young's moduli of the bars making up the bridge are assumed to be uncertain. We choose $\epsilon = 0.05$, $\beta = 10^{-8}$. The relative uncertainty for vertical loads is 0.01 whilst the relative uncertainty for Young's moduli is 0.001. Using software `optimization_generic` (reported next), the following

results are obtained:

$$t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 14202 \\ 18042 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 7242 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 6987 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 7133 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 7142 \\ 17852 \\ 6926 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 14472 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ cm}^3.$$

$$U = 0.49N \times \text{cm}$$

$$V = 10^5 \text{ cm}^3.$$

```
disp('Solver SDP_generic')
```

```
epsilon = 0.05
```

```
beta = 1e-8
```

```
n = num_bars + length(Loads) + 1;
```

```
N = ceil(2/epsilon*log(1/beta) + 2*(n + 1) + 2*(n + 1)/epsilon*log(2/epsilon))
```

```
perc_load = 0.01;
```


Figure 5.14: The .

```

perc_Young = 0.001

t = sdpvar(num_bars, 1);          % cross sectional areas to optimize
CC = set(t(:) >= 0) + set(sum(t) <= V_max)

for ii = 1:N
    YOUNG = E;
    for jj = 1:length(YOUNG)
        YOUNG(jj) = YOUNG(jj)*(1 + perc_Young*(-1 +2*rand));
    end
    invB = diag(YOUNG.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
    FORCES = F;
    for jj = 1:length(LOADS)
        FORCES(2*LOADS(jj)) = FORCES(2*LOADS(jj))*(1 + perc_load*(-1 +2*rand));
    end
    K = A*invB*A';
    gamma = sdpvar(1,1);          % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
    M = [K FORCES; FORCES' gamma];
    CC = CC + set(M >=0);
end

```

```
diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)

t = double(t)
invB = diag(E.*t./(1e4*LENGTHS'.^2));
K = A*invB*A';
disp('Compliance')
U = 1/2*F'*inv(K)*F
disp('Total volume')
sum(t)
```

Chapter 6

Truss structures design with uncertain parameters

This final chapter shows the original prototype that has been used at the beginning of this thesis to solve truss design problems. The effort required by the user is more tedious but this is not a note of demerit at all if the designer has to work with irregular lattices where not all the bars leave from every nodes. Whilst in `bridgeSDP1` the bars are connected automatically here is the user that specifies which bars leaves from every node.

6.1 Nominal load

6.1.1 `truss2008.m`

```
close all
clear all

% %***** RAILROAD BRIDGE *****
% load X_bridge.txt
% load L_bridge.txt
% load fixed_bridge.txt
% load F_bridge.txt
% X = X_bridge           % vector containing nodes coordinates
% L = L_bridge           % vector containing linking bars
% FIXED = fixed_bridge   % vector containing constrained nodes
% F = F_bridge
% %*****

%***** DABBENE AND CALAFIORE'S PAPER *****
load X_Calafiore.txt
load L_Calafiore.txt
```

```

load fixed_Calafiore.txt
load F_Calafiore.txt
X = X_Calafiore           % vector containing nodes coordinates
L = L_Calafiore           % vector containing linking bars
FIXED = fixed_Calafiore   % vector containing constrained nodes
F = F_Calafiore
%*****

m= length(L);             % number of bars
n = length(X);           % number of nodes
N = n - length(FIXED);   % number of free nodes
A = makeA(X, FIXED, L)
LL = givelength(L, X)
dummy = ones(1,m);
% dummy variable to draw equal thickness bars
figure
makegraph(X, L, dummy)
title('INITIAL TRUSS TOPOLOGY')
% F is a vector containing the external applied forces (in components x and y)

% E is a vector containing the Young's moduli of every bar
E = 1e4*ones(1, m)';
bounds = [0 100 1e5];
% bounds = [x_min x_max V_max] known boundaries given by the problem
[x, U] = optimize(A, LL, F, E, bounds);
figure
makegraph(X, L, x)
title('TRUSS TOPOLOGY AFTER OPTIMIZATION')

```

6.1.2 makeA.m

```

% k = number of bars
% p = number of nodes

function A = makeA(X, V, L)
% X: (px2) coordinates of all nodes
% Xv:(nvx1) nodes that are constrained
% L: linking bars
nx = length(X);
A=[];
nl=size(L,1);
for ii = 1:nx
    if isempty(find(V == ii))
        % if node ii is a free node...

```

```

        xi=X(ii,1);
        yi=X(ii,2);
        % finds nodes connected with ii
        [J,v] = find(L == ii);
        % number of nodes connected with node ii
        nn=length(J);
        ax=zeros(1,nn);
        ay=zeros(1,nn);
        for j=1:nn
            Lt=L(J(j),:);
            % index of the linked node
            il=Lt(find(Lt~=ii));
            xj=X(il,1);
            yj=X(il,2);
            theta=atan2(yj-yi,xj-xi);
            ax(J(j))=cos(theta);
            ay(J(j))=sin(theta);
        end
        A=[A;[ax;ay]];
    end
end

```

6.1.3 givelength.m

```

function LL = givelength(L, X)
N = length(L);
for ii = 1:N
    LL(ii) = norm(X(L(ii,1),:)-X(L(ii,2),:));
end
LL=LL(:);

```

6.1.4 makegraph.m

```

function makegraph(X, L, x)
tol = 1e-4;
% tollerance or minimum cross sectional area to draw a bar
plot(X(:,1),X(:,2),'d')
hold on
N = length(L);
for ii = 1:N
    if x(ii) > tol
        line([X(L(ii,1),1),X(L(ii,2),1)], [X(L(ii,1),2),X(L(ii,2),2)],...
            'LineWidth',4*abs(x(ii))/max(x))
    end
end

```

```

end
xmin = min(X(:,1));
xmax = max(X(:,1));
ymin = min(X(:,2));
ymax = max(X(:,2));
axis([xmin-1 xmax+1 ymin-1 ymax+1])

```

6.1.5 optimize.m

```

function [x, U] = optimize(A, LL, f, E, bounds);
% external forces applied to the whole truss at the various nodes are
% collected into the array f
k = length(E);
x = sdpvar(k, 1);      % cross sectional areas to optimize
gamma = sdpvar(1,1);  % upper bound for the compliance of the truss
% The compliance or elastic energy is given by  $U = 1/2*f'*inv(K)*f$ 
invB = diag(E.*x./LL); % diagonal matrix containing the unknowns to optimize
K = A*invB*A';        % Stiffness matrix
M = [ gamma f'; f K];
CC = set(M>0) + set(bounds(1)<=x(:)<=bounds(2)) + ...
     set(LL'*1e3*x<=bounds(3));
% CAUTION!!! Here LL is multiplied by 1e3 because, whilst sections x are
% expressed in mm2, lengths LL are expressed in meters. Hence the same
% unit of measure is required. Here millimeters are used.

diagnostic = solvesdp(CC, gamma)
x = double(x)
invB = diag(E.*x./LL);
K = A*invB*A';
U = 1/2*f'*inv(K)*f

```

6.1.6 An example

This example appeared for the first time in [26, pages 59-78] and it has been solved again using software `truss2008.m`.

Figure 6.1: The truss before optimization.

Figure 6.2: The truss after optimization.

Appendix A

Notation and conventions

- \mathbb{R} is the set of real numbers;
- \mathbb{C} is the set of complex numbers;
- when the context is clear, vectors are not expressed in bold characters and, if not specified, they must be seen as column vectors;
- T denotes the transpose operation;
- $*$ denotes the transpose and conjugate operation; i.e.

$$A^* = (\overline{A})^T;$$

Appendix B

Some linear algebra results

This appendix embraces all the linear algebra concepts exploited in the text. It also encompasses some proofs which will be used for the proof of theorems in the chapters.

B.1 Matrix échelon form, pivots and rank

A common way to solve a system of linear equations is to express it in matrix form $Ax = b$ ($b = 0$ if the system is homogeneous) and consider the augmented matrix

$$\tilde{A} = [A \mid b] \tag{B.1}$$

and reduce it through elementary rows (or columns) operations to an equivalent *reduced row matrix* E such that

1. The nonzero rows of E precede the zero rows;
2. the column numbers of the *leading entries*¹ of the nonzero rows form an increasing sequence of numbers;

i.e. matrix E is in the following form:

$$E = \begin{pmatrix} \circ & * & * & * & * & \dots & * & \dots & * \\ 0 & 0 & \circ & * & * & \dots & * & \dots & * \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \circ & * & \dots & * & \dots & * \\ & & & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & * \\ & & & & & & * & \dots & * \\ & & & & & & 0 & \circ & \dots & * \\ 0 & & & & & & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\ 0 & & & & & & 0 & \dots & 0 & \end{pmatrix}. \tag{B.2}$$

¹A leading entry of a row is the first nonzero entry of that row.

The algorithm who leads matrix \tilde{A} to E is called *Gaussian elimination*. Equivalence means that E is obtained from \tilde{A} through elementary rows or columns operations and involve the same set of solutions of the original system. This is expressed by the notation

$$\hat{A} \sim E.$$

The circles in (B.2) are called *pivots*. Pivots are the leading entries of the rows of matrix E and they progressively appear during Gaussian elimination and are used to zero out entries above or below them by means of elementary row operations.

Moreover matrix E is said to be in *reduced échelon² form* if

1. E is in reduced row matrix form;
2. each leading entry is a 1;
3. each leading entry has only zeros above it;

i.e. matrix E is in the following form:

$$E = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \star & 0 & 0 & \star & \dots & 0 & \dots & \star \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \star & \dots & 0 & \dots & \star \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \star & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \star \\ & & & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \star \\ & & & & & & 0 & \dots & \star \\ & & & & & & 0 & 1 & \dots & \star \\ 0 & & & & & & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\ 0 & & & & & & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

This means that after some *forward* rows (or columns) operations on matrix \hat{A} , one gets an equivalent matrix such as (B.2). With a new set of *back* operations matrix E in échelon form (B.3) is finally obtained and the solutions follows straightforward. Such double way to proceed involving forward and back operations on matrices all equivalent to \hat{A} is called *Gauss-Jordan elimination*.

The number of pivots of a reduced row matrix (or the number of 1 of a reduced échelon row matrix) is called *rank* and is expressed as

$$\text{rank}A$$

There are several definitions for the rank which, of course, give the same result; they are briefly listed here:

²The French word *échelon* means rung, spoke of a ladder.

1. the rank of a matrix \hat{A} is the number of nonzero rows of the reduced row (échelon) form of \hat{A} (the number of zero rows, instead, is the *nullity* and is expressed as $null\hat{A}$);
2. the rank of a matrix \hat{A} is the number of columns of the reduced row échelon form with leading entries in them, since each leading entry of a reduced row échelon form occupies a unique column;

In [27, page 134] it is shown that if $A \sim B$ then B can be obtained from A through left and right multiplication with two *nonsingular* matrices P and Q , i.e.

$$A \sim B \quad \iff \quad B = PAQ \quad P, Q \text{ nonsingular.} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The following theorem (which proof can also be found in [27, pages 136, 137] or [23, pages 94, 113]) provides a more formal definition of rank.

Theorem 11 *Every matrix A $m \times n$ is equivalent to a matrix N_r such that*

$$N_r = \begin{pmatrix} I_r & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix},$$

where r is the rank of matrix A .

Proof Row manipulations on matrix A lead to matrix échelon form E_A having rank r . The columns of E_A having pivots³ are called *basic columns*. Due to definition 2 of rank these columns are r . Applying now column interchanges such that these r basic columns move to the left of E_A , you get a matrix having as (1, 1) entry block the identity matrix I_r . Such a new matrix is equivalent to A which means there exists two nonsingular matrices P_1 and Q_1 such that

$$P_1 A Q_1 = \begin{pmatrix} I_r & J \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{for some matrix } J.$$

Both A and $P_1 A Q_1$ have dimensions $m \times n$ therefore consider a new equivalence using matrices P_2 and Q_2 so defined:

$$P_2 = I_m \quad Q_2 = \begin{pmatrix} I_r & -J \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{pmatrix};$$

then

$$P_2(P_1 A Q_1)Q_2 = I_m \begin{pmatrix} I_r & J \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_r & -J \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{pmatrix} =$$

³Since E_A is in échelon form then the pivots are "1".

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \begin{pmatrix} I_r & J \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_r & -J \\ \mathbf{0} & I \end{pmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} I_r & -J + J \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} I_r & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} = N_r.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $A \sim N_r$ and the theorem is proved. ♣

Matrix N_r is also known as *rank normal form* for A . The last theorem is useful to prove the following one which states that equivalent matrices do not change their rank. The proof can also be found in [27, pages 135, 136].

Theorem 12 *$A \sim B$ if and only if $\text{rank}A = \text{rank}B$.*

Proof If $\text{rank}A = \text{rank}B = r$ then, due to theorem 11 $A \sim N_r$ and $B \sim N_r$ hence $A \sim N_r \sim B$ and, due to transitivity, $A \sim B$. Vice versa if $A \sim B$ and $\text{rank}A = r$ and $\text{rank}B = s$ then, due to theorem 11, $A \sim N_r$ and $B \sim N_s$; therefore $N_r \sim A \sim B \sim N_s$ which, due to transitivity, implies $N_r \sim N_s$, i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_r & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} I_s & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Clearly such equivalence implies $r = s$. ♣

This theorem is the basis for an immediate corollary which is used to prove Sylvester's law of inertia theorem.

Corollary 1 *Multiplication by nonsingular matrices doesn't change the rank.*

Proof In fact if matrix A is multiplied by any nonsingular matrix M conformal to A then this mean to have one of the two matrices P or Q equal to M and the other one equal to I . Therefore an equivalent matrix $B = PAQ$ is formed and, due to theorem 12, the rank doesn't change. ♣

B.2 Vector spaces

As reported in [30, page 150], a vector space over \mathbb{F} is a nonempty set V of elements called vectors, together with operations of vector addition (+) and scalar multiplication (*cdot*), such that the following laws hold for all vectors $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in V$ and scalars $a, b, \in \mathbb{F}$

1. (Closure of vector addition) $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v} \in V$;
2. (Commutativity of addition) $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{u}$;
3. (Associativity of addition) $\mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{w}) = (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{w}$
4. (Additive identity) There exists an element $\mathbf{0} \in V$ such that $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} + \mathbf{u}$;
5. (Additive inverse) There exists an element $-\mathbf{u} \in V$ such that $\mathbf{u} + (-\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{0} = (-\mathbf{u}) + \mathbf{u}$;
6. (Closure of scalar multiplications) $a \cdot \mathbf{u} \in V$;
7. (Distributive law) $a \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) = a \cdot \mathbf{u} + a \cdot \mathbf{v}$;
8. (Distributive law) $(a + b) \cdot \mathbf{u} = a \cdot \mathbf{u} + b \cdot \mathbf{u}$;
9. (Associative law) $(ab) \cdot \mathbf{u} = a \cdot (b \cdot \mathbf{u})$;
10. (Monoidal law) $1 \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}$.

Let S be a subset of vector space V (i.e. $S \subseteq V$) this is said to be a *subspace* of V if it is a vector space on \mathbb{F} with the operations it inherits from V .

B.2.1 Fundamental subspaces

Spanning sets

Given a set of vectors $S = \{\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n\}$, the subspace generated by forming all linear combinations of vectors from S is called *space spanned by* S , i.e.

$$\text{span}S = \{\alpha_1\mathbf{v}_1 + \alpha_2\mathbf{v}_2 + \dots + \alpha_n\mathbf{v}_n\}.$$

Range

For a *linear* function $f(\mathbf{x})$ mapping \mathbb{F}^n into \mathbb{F}^m , the range \mathcal{R} of f is the set of all images as \mathbf{x} varies over \mathbb{F}^n :

$$\mathcal{R}(f) = \{f(\mathbf{x}) \mid \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{F}^n\} \subseteq \mathbb{F}^m.$$

Range space of a matrix

If the linear function from \mathbb{F}^n into \mathbb{F}^m is $f(\mathbf{x}) = A\mathbf{x}$ then the previous definition of range refers to matrix A . In fact

$$\mathcal{R}(A) = \{A\mathbf{x} \mid \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{F}^n\} \subseteq \mathbb{F}^m$$

Such a subspace is also known as *image space of A* . Note that if one partitions matrix A by columns C_i , i.e.

$$A = [C_1 \mid C_2 \mid \dots \mid C_n]$$

then

$$A\mathbf{x} = [C_1 \mid C_2 \mid \dots \mid C_n] \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i C_i = \text{span}\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}.$$

This means that the set of all images $A\mathbf{x}$ is the same as the set of all linear combinations of the columns of A , i.e. $\text{span}\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$. That's why the range (or image) space of A is also called *column space of A* and is also expressed as

$$\text{colsp } A = \mathcal{R}(A).$$

Similarly

$$\mathcal{R}(A^T) = \{A^T \mathbf{y} \mid \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{F}^m\} \subseteq \mathbb{F}^n$$

But $\mathcal{R}(A^T) = \text{colsp } A^T$ and the columns of A^T are the rows of A so $\mathcal{R}(A^T)$ is just the space spanned by the rows of A . That's why the range (or image) space of A^T is also called *row space of A* and is also expressed as

$$\text{rowsp } A = \mathcal{R}(A^T).$$

Nullspace

Consider again a *linear* function $f(\mathbf{x})$ from \mathbb{F}^n into \mathbb{F}^m then the set of vectors mapped to $\mathbf{0}$ is called *nullspace (or kernel) of f* , i.e.

$$\mathcal{N}(f) = \ker(f) = \{\mathbf{x} \mid f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}\}.$$

The nullspace is a subset of \mathbb{F}^n in fact given two distinct $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathcal{N}(f)$ (i.e. $f(\mathbf{x}_1) = f(\mathbf{x}_2) = \mathbf{0}$) then, due to linearity of f

$$f(\alpha\mathbf{x}_1 + \beta\mathbf{x}_2) = \alpha f(\mathbf{x}_1) + \beta f(\mathbf{x}_2) = \alpha\mathbf{0} + \beta\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0} + \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0} \in \mathcal{N}(f).$$

Applying again the definition to linear matrix function $A\mathbf{x}$ then

$$\mathcal{N}(A) = \ker(A) = \{\mathbf{x} \mid A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}\}.$$

B.2.2 Basis and dimension

A linear independent spanning set \mathcal{B} for a vector space V is called a basis for \mathcal{B} . A standard basis for \mathbb{R}^n are the *unit vectors* $\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n\}$; where

$$\mathbf{e}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix};$$

with a 1 in position i . The dimension of a vector space V is defined to be the number of vectors in any basis for V and is expressed as $\dim V$. Given two subspaces U and W of V it can be proved (see, for instance, [23, page 160] or [27, pages 166, 167]) that the set $U + W$ is again a subspace of V . Also $U \cap W$ is a subspace of V (see, for instance [23, page 128]) for a proof). The next theorem gives a result useful for the proof of Sylvester's law of inertia theorem and gives the dimension of the sum of two subspaces given the dimension of the single subspaces and the dimension of the intersection of the two subspaces.

Theorem 13 *If U and W are subspaces of a vector space V then*

$$\dim(U + W) = \dim U + \dim W - \dim(U \cap W)$$

Proof Let $\dim(U \cap W) = t$, $\dim U = m + t$ and $\dim W = n + t$ for some integers m , n and t and let $\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t\}$ be a basis for $U \cap W$ then there must be some extension vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2, \dots, \mathbf{u}_m\}$ and $\{\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_n\}$ such that

$$\mathcal{B}_U = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2, \dots, \mathbf{u}_m\} \quad \text{is a basis for } U$$

$$\mathcal{B}_W = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_n\} \quad \text{is a basis for } W.$$

Obviously $\text{span}(\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W) = U + W$ but if prove that $\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W$ is a linearly independent set⁴ then it is also a basis for $\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W$ which dimension gives

⁴A set of vectors $\{\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n\}$ is said to be independent if the only linear combination (sometimes called *trivial solution*) which gives zero is the one having all zero scalar coefficients, i.e.

$$\alpha_1 \mathbf{v}_1 + \dots + \alpha_n \mathbf{v}_n = 0 \text{ iff } \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n = 0.$$

$\dim(\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W)$. Consider a linear combination of vectors of set $\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W$ and put it equal to zero as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k = 0.$$

Then

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k = -\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i - \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j = -\left(\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j \right). \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Nota that at the second side of equation (B.5) there's a linear combination of vectors \mathbf{z}_i and \mathbf{u}_j which belong to basis \mathcal{B}_U hence

$$-\left(\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j \right) \in U.$$

Therefore, due to equality (B.5)

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k \in U.$$

Nevertheless $\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k$ is a linear combinations of \mathbf{w}_k which belong to basis \mathcal{B}_W hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k \in W;$$

therefore

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k \in U \cap W.$$

Now, since $\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k \in U \cap W$ and a basis of $U \cap W$ is $\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t\}$ then there must exist some scalars δ_i such that a linear combination of \mathbf{z}_i will give $\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k \in U \cap W$; i.e.

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \delta_i \mathbf{z}_i = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k$$

or

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \delta_i \mathbf{z}_i - \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k = 0. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Note that (B.6) is a linear combination forced to zero of vectors \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{w} which belong to basis \mathcal{B}_W which is an independent set therefore the only scalar values able to satisfy (B.6) are

$$\delta_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_k = 0.$$

Substituting $\gamma_k = 0$ in (B.5) gives

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j = 0. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

This is another linear combination forced to zero this time of vectors \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{u} which belong to basis \mathcal{B}_U which is an independent set therefore the only scalar values able to satisfy (B.7) are

$$\alpha_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_j = 0.$$

This means that all the scalar coefficients α_i , β_j and γ_k must be zero therefore the only possible solution for the original linear combination of vectors of set $\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W$

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i \mathbf{z}_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \mathbf{u}_j + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \mathbf{w}_k = 0.$$

is the trivial solution. This means that $\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W$ is an independent set therefore it is a basis for $U + W$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \dim(U + W) &= \dim(\mathcal{B}_U \cup \mathcal{B}_W) = \\ &= t + m + n = \\ &= (t + m) + (t + n) - t = \\ &= \dim U + \dim W - \dim(U \cap W). \end{aligned}$$

♣

B.3 Congruent matrices

Let $A, B \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}$. If there exist a *nonsingular* matrix G such that

- $B = G^*AG$ then B is said to be **congruent* (star congruent or *conjunctive*) to A ;
- $B = G^T AG$ then B is said to be *T congruent* (tee congruent) to A .

Congruency is expressed by the symbol \cong i.e. $B \cong A$ means that matrix B is congruent to matrix A .

The next and even more results on congruent matrices can also be found in [21, page 250 and ahead].

Theorem 14 *Congruent matrices have the same rank.*

Proof Since, by definition, G is nonsingular, the thesis follows by corollary 1.

Theorem 15 *Both $*$ and T congruence are **equivalence relations**⁵, that is, for any $A \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}$*

1. (*Reflexivity*) A is congruent to A ;
2. (*Symmetry*) If A is congruent to B then B is congruent to A ;
3. (*Transitivity*) If A is congruent to B and B is congruent to C then A is congruent to C .

Proof

1. To prove this point it is enough to set $G = I$; in fact $I^* = I$ and $G^*AG = I^*AI = IAI = A$ hence A is congruent to A ;
2. If A is congruent to B then $A = G^*BG$ for some nonsingular matrix G . Developing this expression we have $(G^*)^{-1}A = BG$. But $(G^*)^{-1} = (G^{-1})^*$ hence $(G^{-1})^*A = BG$ and $(G^{-1})^*AG^{-1} = B$. This means that B is congruent to A through matrix G^{-1} ;
3. If A is congruent to B then, for some nonsingular G_1 , $A = G_1^*BG_1$. If B is congruent to C then, for some nonsingular G_2 , $B = G_2^*CG_2$. Putting altogether we have: $A = G_1^*BG_1 = G_1^*G_2^*CG_2G_1 = (G_2G_1)^*C(G_2G_1)$; therefore A is congruent to C through matrix G_2G_1 .

⁵For details about equivalence relations, see [38, pages 87-90].

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